

Notes on some taxa of the *Alvania lineata*-complex with the descriptions of three new species from the Mediterranean Sea (Gastropoda: Rissoidae)

Notas sobre algunos taxones del complejo de *Alvania lineata*, con la descripción de tres nuevas especies del Mediterráneo (Gastropoda: Rissoidae)

Bruno AMATI*¹, Massimo APPOLLONI**², Ermanno QUAGGIOTTO***³,
Carlo SMRIGLIO****⁴ & Marco OLIVERIO*****⁵

Recibido el 9-X-2018. Aceptado el 28-XII-2018

ABSTRACT

Some taxonomically troublesome nominal taxa of the rissoid genus *Alvania* Risso, 1826 are examined: *Alvania disparilis* Monterosato, 1890, *A. peloritana* (Aradas & Benoit, 1874), *A. perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972 and *A. dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826). The four species are here considered as valid, and for the sake of nomenclatural stability lectotypes of *Alvania disparilis*, *Rissoa peloritana* and *Alvania perversa* are designated. The holotype of *Alvania dorbignyi* is refigured and redescribed, and all Mediterranean records of this species are reassigned to *A. perversa*. *Alvania schwartziana* Brusina, 1866 is reported for the first time in Italian waters. Three new species are herein described: *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., *Alvania unica* n. sp. and *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp.

RESUMEN

Se examinan algunos taxones nominales problemáticos de risóidos del género *Alvania* Risso, 1826: *Alvania disparilis* Monterosato, 1890, *A. peloritana* (Aradas y Benoit, 1874), *A. perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972 y *A. dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826). Las cuatro especies se consideran aquí válidas, y con fines de mantener la estabilidad nomenclatural se designan lectotipos de *Alvania disparilis*, *Rissoa peloritana* y *Alvania perversa*. El holotipo de *Alvania dorbignyi* está figurado de nuevo y redescrito, y todas las citas de esta especie en el Mediterráneo se reconducen a *A. perversa*. *Alvania schwartziana* Brusina, 1866 se cita por primera vez en aguas italianas. Se describen tres nuevas especies: *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., *Alvania unica* n. sp. y *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp.

* Largo Giuseppe Veratti, 37/D, 00146 Rome, Italy; e-mail: bruno_amati@yahoo.it

** Museo Civico di Zoologia, Via Ulisse Aldrovandi, 18, 00197 Rome, Italy; e-mail: massimo.appolloni@comune.roma.it

*** Via Secula 13, 36023 Longare, Vicenza, Italy; e-mail: ermanno.quaggitto@libero.it

**** Department of Science, "Roma Tre" University of Rome, Viale Marconi, 446, 00146 Rome, Italy; e-mail: csmriglio@alice.it

***** Department of Biology and Biotechnologies "Charles Darwin", Sapienza University of Rome, Viale dell'Università 32, I-00185 Rome, Italy; e-mail: marco.oliverio@uniroma1.it

¹ Corresponding author

INTRODUCTION

Rissoidae Gray, 1847 is the most diverse rissooidean family, with at least 38 recognised genera (ÁVILA, 2005; CRISCIONE & PONDER, 2013; MOLLUSCABASE, 2018). The genus *Alvania* Risso, 1826 is currently represented by 314 recognised species of which 263 belonging to the Recent fauna (MOLLUSCABASE, 2018). In the Mediterranean Sea the genus *Alvania* is largely represented by 72 Recent species (MOLLUSCABASE, 2018) and includes several species-complex, e.g. *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826, *Alvania dictyophora* (Philippi, 1844), *Alvania scabra* (Philippi, 1844) and *Alvania subcrenulata* (Bucquoy, Dautzenberg & Dollfus, 1884). Among them the *Alvania lineata*-complex includes some 20 recognised Recent species (Table I), all with non-planktotrophic development, except for *Alvania discors* (Allan, 1818) which has a planktotrophic larval stage.

Traditionally, the taxonomy of Mediterranean rissoids has been based almost exclusively on shell characters, whose puzzling variation has often caused uncertainty about the status of some of these taxa. Although an integrated approach (teleoconch, protoconch, soft parts morphology and colour pattern, radula, genetics, etc...) will certainly help in assessing their taxonomy, however, in most cases, the availability of large samples and the comparative study of type material provide important data to improve current taxonomic knowledge. In this note, we focused on four nominal taxa of this complex, of uncertain status: *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826), *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972, *Alvania peloritana* (Aradas & Benoit, 1874) and *Alvania disparilis* Monterosato, 1890, and describe three additional new species.

Description of the *A. lineata* group

All the species in the complex have rather similar shells: thick, of medium-large size for the genus, with ovate-conical profile, wide base, and rather

strong teleoconch sculpture, the spiral usually weaker than the axial; strong apertural varix in mature specimens, outer lip usually with denticles on the inner side (except for *Alvania datchaensis* Amati & Oliverio, 1987 and *A. claudioi* Buzzurro & Landini, 2007); protoconch paucispiral indicating a non-planktotrophic larval development, except for *Alvania discors* (Allan, 1818), rarely devoid of an apparent sculpture (e.g. *Alvania algeriana* (Monterosato, 1877, *Alvania claudioi*, *Alvania bozcaadensis* Tiselli & Giunchi, 2013 and *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp.), usually sculptured by numerous microtubercles randomly arranged or fused to form parallel minute threads, or more rarely by flattened cordlets arranged into an orange skin pattern (e.g. *Alvania lanciae* (Calcara, 1845)) or zigzag patterns (e.g. *Alvania datchaensis* Amati & Oliverio, 1987). Shell with usually uniformly coloured background with or without more or less fine or interrupted spiral bands. The external soft parts have been described for a few species and are conforming to the general scheme of the genus *Alvania* (e.g. BRUSINA, 1866: 25 for *Alvania schwartziana* Brusina, 1866; PONDER, 1985: 38 for *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826; AMATI & NOFRONI, 1985: 19; ALBANO & SABELLI, 2009: 56 for *Alvania settepassii* Amati & Nofroni, 1985).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The samples here studied are stored in public and private collections, as detailed under each species (see abbreviations), and in the Appendix. Photographs have been taken with a Sony Cyber-Shot digital camera mounted on a Kyowa KBS stereomicroscope, edited with the Combine-Z software (HADLEY, 2006). Most SEM photographs were taken with a Philips XL30 at the Interdepartmental Laboratory of Electron Microscopy (LIME: University "Roma Tre", Rome); the SEM photos of the holotype of *Alvania garrafensis* are courtesy of Emilio Rolán (Vigo); that of the type of *Alvania dorbignyi* is courtesy of

Table I. List of the Mediterranean species of the *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826 complex.
 Tabla I. Lista de las especies mediterráneas del complejo *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826.

Species	Figures
<i>Alvania aeoliae</i> Palazzi, 1988	Figure 67
<i>Alvania algeriana</i> (Monterosato, 1877)	Figure 72
<i>Alvania aspera</i> (Philippi, 1844)	Figure 77
<i>Alvania bartolinorum</i> Amati & Smriglio n. sp.	Figures 30-40
<i>Alvania bozcaadensis</i> Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013	Figures 63, 64
<i>Alvania campanii</i> Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013	Figures 65, 66
<i>Alvania claudioi</i> Buzzurro & Landini, 2007	Figure 58
<i>Alvania colossophilus</i> Oberling, 1970	Figure 76
<i>Alvania datchaensis</i> Amati & Oliverio, 1987	Figures 68, 69
<i>Alvania discors</i> (Allan, 1818)	Figure 55
<i>Alvania disparilis</i> Monterosato, 1890	Figures 1-11
<i>Alvania dorbignyi</i> (Audouin, 1826)	Figures 19-22
<i>Alvania elisae</i> Margelli, 2001	Figures 78, 79
<i>Alvania fractospira</i> Oberling, 1970	Figures 70, 71
<i>Alvania garrafensis</i> Peñas & Rolán, 2008	Figures 73-75
<i>Alvania lanciae</i> (Calcara, 1845)	Figures 59-61
<i>Alvania lineata</i> Risso, 1826	Figure 62
<i>Alvania peloritana</i> (Aradas & Benoit, 1874)	Figures 12-18
<i>Alvania perversa</i> Nordsieck, 1972 = <i>Alvania dorbignyi</i> AA non (Audouin, 1826)	Figures 23-29
<i>Alvania schwartziana</i> Brusina, 1866	Figure 57
<i>Alvania settepassii</i> Amati & Nofroni, 1985	Figure 56
<i>Alvania unica</i> Amati & Quaggiotto n. sp.	Figures 41-48
<i>Alvania zaraensis</i> Amati & Appolloni n. sp.	Figures 49-54

the MNHN (Paris); those of the types of *Alvania perversa* are courtesy of S. Hof (SRI, Frankfurt am Main). Measurements for the new species were taken from 25 specimens of *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp. and 12 specimens of *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. (Tables II-III).

Abbreviations and acronyms

AN: Andrea Nappo collection (Quartu Sant'Elena, Italy);
 AP: Attilio Pagli collection (Vinci, Florence, Italy);
 AR: Alessandro Raveggi collection (Florence, Italy)
 BA: Bruno Amati collection (Rome, Italy)
 CB: Cesare Bogi collection (Livorno, Italy)
 CS-PM: Carlo Smriglio–Paolo Mariottini collection (Rome, Italy)

EQ: Ermanno Quaggiotto collection (Longare, Vicenza, Italy)
 IN: Italo Nofroni collection (Rome, Italy)
 MBAC: Museum of the Department of Animal Biology of the University (Catania, Italy)
 CMSN: Museum of Natural History (Milan, Italy)
 MGPUF: Geological Museum and Palaeontology of the University (Florence, Italy)
 MCZR: Zoological Museum (Rome, Italy)
 MNHN: National Museum of Natural History (Paris, France)
 MO: Marco Oliverio collection (Rome, Italy)
 RP: Raffaele Petrone (Rome, Italy)
 SG: Serge Gofas collection (University of Malaga)

SB-MS: Stefano Bartolini-Maria Scape-
rotta collection, (Florence, Italy)

SEM: scanning electron microscope

SMF: Senckenberg Museum (Frankfurt
am Main, Germany)

Teleoconch=

H: height

W: width

Ha: height of the aperture

H/W: ratio height/width

Nw: number of whorls

Nar: number of axial ribs

Nsc-ab: number of spiral cords above
the aperture

Nsc-ba: number of spiral cords on the base
Protoconch =

h: height

d: diameter of nucleus

Do: diameter of first half whorl

DM: maximum diameter

nw: number of whorls

sh: empty shell(s)

lv: live collected specimen(s) with soft
parts.

SYSTEMATICS

Class GASTROPODA Cuvier, 1795

Subclass CAENOGASTROPODA Cox, 1960

Superfamily RISSOIDEA Gray, 1847

Family RISSOIDAE Gray, 1847

Genus *Alvania* Risso, 1826: 140

Type-species: *Alvania europea* Risso, 1826: 142, pl. IX, fig. 116 = *Alvania cimex* (Linnaeus, 1758)
(*Turbo*), by subsequent designation NEVILL, 1885: 105

Alvania disparilis Monterosato, 1890 (Figs. 1-11)

Alvania disparilis Monterosato, 1890: 146

Type material: Lectotype (MCZR-M-22155/L, Monterosato coll.) (Figs 1-4), here designated (H 2.95 mm, W 1.75 mm) and 25 paralectotypes (MCZR-M-22155/P, Monterosato coll.) (mostly fragments), from the type locality, 1 paralectotype (MCZR-M-22155/P, Monterosato coll.) from Sciacca, Sicily.

Other material examined: Sicily. Messina, labelled, "R. Peloritana, subfoss. del Porto di Messina", 6 sh (of which some broken) (MCZR-M-22150, Monterosato coll.); Messina, labelled "?Duccinella! Messina! / *Alvania peloritana*", 4 sh (MCZR-M-30053, Monterosato coll.); unspecified locality, 5 sh (MCZR-M-30054, Monterosato coll.).

Type locality: Off Palermo (Sicily, Italy), 'Funnazzi', unspecified depth.

Distribution: Central Mediterranean: off Palermo and Messina (Sicily), at unspecified depth, possibly ca. 90-180 m depth (ca. 50-100 'braccia') for off Palermo. The site name 'Funnazzi' indicates an enigmatic fishing area off Palermo, repeatedly cited by Monterosato and de Gregorio (DE GREGORIO, 1889a: 248; 1889b: 7, 8); traces of its location have been lost even among local fishermen (see APOLLONI ET AL., 2018: table 1).

Description of the lectotype: Shell (Figs 1-4) small, not solid, ovate-conic, globose, height 2.95 mm, width 1.75

mm, H/W 1.68, aperture 1.45 mm. Protoconch (Figs 3, 4) height 0.375 mm, globose, paucispiral, of 1.6 whorls, diameter of nucleus 0.15 mm, diameter of first half whorl 0.25 mm, maximum diameter 0.425 mm; sculpture of a dozen interrupted spiral cordlets, becoming finer and more numerous toward the protoconch/teleoconch boundary. Teleoconch of 3.4 convex whorls, suture canalculated. Axial sculpture on the last whorl of 14 fine orthocline ribs, half as wide as the interspaces, interrupted at the suprasutural spiral cordlet. Spiral sculpture starting

Figures 1-11. *Alvania disparilis* Monterosato, 1890. 1: lectotype, Palermo (Sicily), H 2.95 mm (MCZR-M-22155/L); 2, 3: SEM micrograph of the lectotype; 4: detail of the protoconch sculpture of the lectotype; 5: original label; 6: shell from Messina (Sicily) (MCZR-M-22150), H 2.8 mm; 7: original label of the same shell; 8: SEM micrograph of the same shell; 9-11: details of the protoconch.

Figuras 1-11. Alvania disparilis Monterosato, 1890. 1: lectotipo, Palermo (Sicilia), H 2,95 mm (MCZR-M-22155/L); 2, 3: micrografía electrónica de barrido del lectotipo; 4: detalle de la escultura de la protoconcha del lectotipo; 5: etiqueta original; 6: concha de Messina (Sicilia) (MCZR-M-22150), H 2,8 mm; 7: etiqueta original de la misma concha; 8: micrografía electrónica de barrido de la misma concha; 9-11: detalles de la protoconcha.

with 2 (II and IV) visible fine spiral cordlets on early teleoconch; on the last whorl 9 (4+1+4) cordlets, the four adapical ones equidistant and twice as wide as the interspaces, the others slightly closer at first and then spaced with increasing distance abapically; minute tubercles at the intersection of axial ribs and spirals cordlets, forming a quadrangular reticulate pattern. Coloration light brown, with protoconch and spiral cordlets slightly darker. Soft parts and operculum unknown.

Remarks: The original material of *Alvania disparilis* Monterosato, 1890 (MCZR-M-22155, Monterosato coll.) (APPOLLONI ET AL., 2018: 43, pl. 14, figs C, D), consists of two vials: one contains 26 syntypes, mostly fragments, from 'Funazzì', off Palermo, Sicily, with autograph label by Monterosato reading: "Al. disparilis, Monts. mss. 1890 Palermo 1886!" (Fig. 5). The best-preserved shell is here selected as lectotype (Figs 1-4), to stabilize the name usage. This same shell was figured by CAMPANI, BARTOLINI & SPANU (2012: 89, fig. 7) with erroneous measurement (H 3.6 mm instead of H 2.95 mm) to compare with *A. garrafensis* sensu CAMPANI, BARTOLINI & SPANU, 2012 (= *A. bartolinorum* n. sp. this work, not *A. garrafensis* Peñas & Rolán, 2008). The other vial contains a single shell, from off Sciacca, Sicily, also with autograph label by Monterosato reading: "Sciacca" (Figs 41-48). This shell is not conspecific with the specimens from off Palermo, and represents indisputably an undescribed species, which will be described below (*Alvania unica* n. sp.). *Alvania disparilis* Monterosato, 1890 has been considered as a deep-water form of *Alvania lanciae* (Calcara, 1845) (K. Nicolay and G. Schirò in VAN AARTSEN, 1982: 4).

Alvania lanciae (Calcara, 1845) (:29, pl. IV, fig. 12) (Figs 59-61) differs from *Alvania disparilis* by its conspicuously microsculptured teleoconch (lacking in *A. disparilis*) and by the protoconch sculpture of irregular pits, with an orange-skin like pattern, vs. a dozen interrupted spiral cordlets in *A. disparilis*. Furthermore, *A. lanciae* has usually a more robust shell, with large nodules at the intersections, slightly elongated along the spirals, gradually stronger toward the base, vs. weaker minute tubercles in *A. disparilis*, and the spiral sculpture above the aperture is irregularly spaced vs. equidistant and finer in *A. disparilis*.

Alvania garrafensis Peñas & Rolán, 2008 (:21, figs 8-13) (Figs 73-75) has a weaker spiral sculpture, particularly on the first whorls, slightly stronger only on the base but not overrunning the axial one (in *Alvania disparilis* the spiral sculpture is on the whole teleoconch and the intersection with the axials forms a quadrangular reticulation and minute tubercles); the axials are hardly visible on the first whorl, are rounded and orthocone with an evident shoulder (in *Alvania disparilis* the axials are fine and orthocone, lacking any shoulder, and visible from the first whorl). The outline and the protoconch sculpture are similar.

Alvania lineata Risso, 1826 (:142, pl. IX, fig. 120) (Fig. 62) differs from *Alvania disparilis* by its more robust shell reaching a larger size, with a more slender outline, with more marked and nodulose sculpture (axial and spiral), with axials reaching the base, a robust varix and a more slender protoconch.

See also remarks under *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., *Alvania unica* n. sp. and *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. for the differences with these species.

Alvania peloritana (Aradas & Benoit, 1874) [new status] (Figs. 12-18)

Rissoa (Alvania) peloritana Aradas & Benoit, 1874: 205, pl. IV, fig. 16

Type material: lectotype (MCZR-M-22150/L, Monterosato coll. ex Benoit) (Figs 12, 13), here designated (H 3.35 mm, W 1.88 mm), and 1 paralectotype (MCZR-M-22150/P, Monterosato coll. ex Benoit) (Fig 16, 17; H 3.0 mm, W 1.62 mm) from the type locality.

Type locality: Messina, Sicily, Italy, unspecified depth.

Figures 12-18. *Alvania peloritana* Aradas & Benoit, 1874. 12, 13: lectotype, Messina (Sicily), H 3.35 mm (MCZR-M-22150/L); 14, 15: original labels; 16, 17: paralectotype, Messina, H 3 mm (MCZR-M-22150/P); 18: original drawings (reproduced from ARADAS & BENOIT, 1874: pl. IV, fig. 16).

Figuras 12-18. Alvania peloritana Aradas y Benoit, 1874. 12, 13: lectotipo, Messina (Sicilia), H 3,35 mm (MCZR-M-22150/L); 14, 15: etiquetas originales; 16, 17: paralectotipo, Messina, H 3 mm (MCZR-M-22150/P); 18: dibujos originales (reproducidos de ARADAS & BENOIT, 1874: pl. IV, fig. 16).

Distribution: Central Mediterranean Sea: Messina (Sicily), Italy, unspecified depth. Aradas and Benoit reported it from the Messina harbour, sympatric with *Alvania cimex* and *Alvania montagui*.

Description of the lectotype: Shell (Figs 12, 13) small, solid, ovate-conical, rather slender, height 3.35 mm, width 1.88 mm, height aperture 1.45 mm, H/W 1.78. Protoconch paucispiral, of 1.3 slightly convex whorls with adapical shoulder, height 0.30 mm, diameter of nucleus

0.14 mm, diameter of first half whorl 0.30 mm, maximum diameter 0.40 mm. Protoconch sculpture constituted by small tubercles, often fused, forming series of spirals cords.

Teleoconch of 4.1 convex whorls, suture canalculated. Axial sculpture of 10 orthocline rounded ribs on the last whorl, as wide as half the interspaces, overrunning the suprasutural spiral cordlet.

Spiral sculpture starting with 2 (II and IV) visible fine spiral cordlets on

early teleoconch. On the last whorl 8 (4+1+3) cordlets, equidistant and as wide as twice the interspaces, slightly passing over the axials. Quadrangular cancellation by the intersection of axials and spirals. Apertural varix weak. Columellar wall angled medially. Umbilical chink very narrow. Teleoconch without visible microsculpture (90X). Coloration light brown, with whitish axial ribs and columellar area, white apertural varix, some spiral and slightly darker cordlets. Soft parts unknown, typical operculum of the genus, thin, corneous, with eccentric nucleus.

Remarks: In the lot of *Alvania peloritana* (Aradas & Benoit, 1874) in the Monterosato collection (MCZR-M-22150, ex Benoit), one vial contains two specimens with the soft parts dried inside, (Figs 12, 13; 16, 17) with autograph labels by Benoit reading: "Riss. Peloritana Messina" and "Riss. Peloritana Messina Lazzaretto - Weinkauff la riguarda come varietà della Montagui" (Figs 14, 15). Those specimens represent the only known type material of this taxon. The type material of *A. peloritana* has not been found either in the Aradas collection in Milano (MCSN) (G. BUZZURRO, pers. comm. 2007), or in Catania (MBAC) (D. SCUDERI, pers. comm. 2014), where there is other type material of Aradas (SCUDERI, 2007: 125; SCUDERI & AMATI, 2013: 511).

The actual identity of *Alvania peloritana* has long been controversial, the taxon having been considered either as a nomen dubium, or as a variety, synonym or subspecies of either *Alvania discors* or *Alvania lineata* (e.g. MONTEROSATO, 1872: 36; 1875: 27; 1878: 84; GRANATA-GRILLO, 1877: 147; F. NORDSIECK, 1972: 195; MARÍN & ROS, 1987: 139; PALAZZI, 1997: 36; SCUDERI & TERLIZZI, 2012: 50; MOLLUSCABASE, 2018). The original description and the iconography, along with the extreme shell variability in the *Alvania lineata*-group, contributed to the uncertainty. Furthermore, there is an issue raised by PALAZZI (1997: 35), on the probable inversion of the figures in the original work. The available type material of *A.*

peloritana matches satisfactorily both the original description and the figures (ARADAS & BENOIT, 1874: 205, pl. IV, fig. 16), with the possible exception of the simple and acute outer lip ("Il labro è semplice ed acuto"). The two specimens (lectotype and paralectotype) have a weakly developed apertural varix and the paralectotype shows very weak internal denticles. These features are more marked in *A. discors* and *A. lineata*.

A. peloritana shows intermediate features between *A. discors* and *A. lineata*, so that Weinkauff (fide Benoit, see original label) (Fig. 14) and PALAZZI (1997: 36) considered it as a synonym of *A. montagui* and *A. lineata*, respectively.

The specimen from Messina (Sicily) recently figured as *A. peloritana* by VILLARI & SCUDERI (2017: 197, fig. 21) does not match the type material of *A. peloritana* and rather corresponds to an unusual form of *A. lineata* with sculpture of the teleoconch less marked.

Alvania discors (Allan, 1818) (:463, pl. X, fig. 5) (Fig. 55), differs from *Alvania peloritana* in the multispiral protoconch (vs. paucispiral in *A. peloritana*), the larger size, the almost flat whorls (v. slightly convex in *A. peloritana*), the interrupted axials (v. overrunning the suprasutural cordlet in *A. peloritana*), the variable and polychrome coloration (v. almost monochrome in *A. peloritana*).

Alvania lineata Risso, 1826 (:142, pl. IX, fig. 120) (Fig. 62) differs mainly in the larger size, the spiral and axial sculpture more marked, the axials reaching well beyond the periphery, in the marked tubercles at the intersections of axial and spiral sculptures, in the more robust apertural varix, and in the more protruded apex. The protoconch of *A. peloritana* observed at 90 \leftrightarrow magnification, shows a sculpture similar to that of *A. lineata* (e.g. PONDER, 1985: 135, fig. 86B; GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011: 181, unnumbered figure) but finer.

See also remarks under *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., *Alvania unica* n. sp. and *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. for the differences with these species.

Alvania dorbignyi (Audouin, 1826) (Figs. 19-22)

Rissoa D'Orbignyi Audouin, 1826:171 [based on SAVIGNY, 1817: pl. III, fig. 22]

Type material: holotype (Figs 19-22) H 2.45 mm, W 1.35 mm (type loc.) (MNHN-IM-2000-27705 Paris).

Type locality: unspecified [scope of the publication is Egypt, most of the material from the Red Sea].

Distribution: unknown (see below).

Description of the holotype: Shell (Figs 19-22) small, solid, ovate-conical, rather slender, height 2.45 mm, width 1.35 mm and height of aperture 1 mm, H/W 1.81. Protoconch paucispiral (Fig. 22), of barely convex whorls with an adapical shoulder. Protoconch sculpture not visible (apparently smooth).

Teleoconch of 4+ slightly convex whorls, suture canalculated and undulated. Axial sculpture of 10 opisthoclinal rounded ribs on the last whorl (orthocline and then slightly flexuose on the first whorls), as wide as the interspaces (more spaced on the last half whorl), interrupted immediately below the suprasutural spiral cordlet. Spiral sculpture weak; on the last whorl 5 well spaced spiral cordlets on the base and one in correspondence with the suture, the upper part apparently devoid of spirals. Apertural varix strong, with 8 elongate internal denticles. Columellar wall angled medially. Coloration light brown-beige. Soft parts and operculum unknown.

Remarks: It has not yet been defined with certainty whether *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826) (Figs 19-22) is a native Mediterranean species (MIENIS, 1985: 652; ÖZTÜRK, BUZZURRO & AVNI BENLI, 2004: 68; MIENIS, 2005: 104), or an Indo-Pacific immigrant (F. NORDSIECK, 1972b: 230; AMATI & NOFRONI, 1985: 23; BARASH & DANIN, 1992: 54; ZENETOS, GOFAS, RUSSO & TEMPLADO, 2004; ÁVILA, 2005: 43; DELONGUEVILLE & SCAILLET, 2007: 58). It is thus considered as cryptogenic (GOFAS & ZENETOS, 2003). This issue arises since SAVIGNY (1817: pl. III, fig. 22) during Napoleon's Egyptian campaign, sampled terrestrial, freshwater and marine molluscs in both the Red Sea and the Mediterranean,

and the holotype of *Rissoa dorbignyi* Audouin was among that material, apparently without clear collecting data. However, the marine samples are commonly assumed having all been collected in the Red Sea, based on ISSEL (1869: 6) ["Ne risultarono per la parte malacologica 18 tavole in foglio mirabilmente eseguite, che rappresentano circa 220 specie marine dell'Eritreo e più di 30 terrestri e fluviatili dell'Egitto."]. We thus, follow here the common assumption that *Rissoa dorbignyi* Audouin was collected in the Red Sea, is/was a Red Sea species, possibly not extending northward beyond the Suez area ["Elle est très rare dans les sables de la baie de Suez." (MOAZZO, 1939: 185)]. There is a moderately rich rissoid fauna in the Red Sea, with at least the following genera represented: *Manzonina* Brusina, 1870, *Parashiela* Laseron, 1856, *Rissoa* Desmarest, 1814, *Setia* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1852 *Voorwindia* Ponder, 1985, *Lucidestea* Laseron, 1956, *Cingula* Fleming, 1818, *Ceratia* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1852, *Onoba* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1852, *Rissoina* d'Orbigny, 1840, *Schwartziella* G. Nevill, 1881, *Stosicia* Brusina, 1870 and *Zebina* H. Adams & A. Adams, 1854 (ISSEL, 1869: 291; PALLARY, 1926: 57; HORNUNG & MERMOD, 1927: 364; MOAZZO, 1939: 185; DEKKER & ORLIN, 2000: 20; JANSSEN, ZUSCHIN & BAAL, 2011: 383) Although the genus *Alvania* has not been confirmed (DEKKER & ORLIN, 2000: 20) its presence cannot be completely ruled out (MOAZZO, 1939: 185).

Iconography of shells under the name "*Alvania dorbignyi*" in the recent literature is scanty and we could not find any ascertained Mediterranean record of a properly identified spec-

imen. DELONGUEVILLE & SCAILLET (2007: 55, fig. 24) figured under *A. dorbignyi* a shell of *A. perversa*; CAMPANI (2008: 1, fig. 2) a shell of *A. discors*; F. NORDSIECK (1972b: 231, figs 13, 14) figured *A. dorbignyi* and *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972, respectively, but his figure 13, showed in fact a 'dorbignized' *A. perversa* (a sort of iconographic stretching, certainly not uncommon in Nordsieck's works, see PALAZZI, 1997: 36).

The holotype of *Rissoa dorbignyi* figured by BOUCHET & DANRIGAL (1982: 21, fig. 68) and rephotographed here (Figs 20-22) seems therefore to be the only known specimen of that species and shows diagnostic features with respect to the native Mediterranean species of the genus commonly confused under the name *A. dorbignyi*. The holotype has a paucispiral protoconch, as most species of the *Alvania lineata*-complex, but more slender; the small shell (H 2.5 mm) is smaller than the averages of the other species; the spiral sculpture is very weak to faint with only a few evident basal cordlets, whereas in the other species it is always present, more or less strong; the axial ribs are flat, broad and as wide as the interspaces *vs.* never flat (acute and/or rounded) in the other species with the exception of *A. settepassii*. Issel (1869: 205) described the figure of Savigny erroneously including spiral coloured stripes ["...Alla base di ciascun giro vedonsi, nella figura, parecchie fasce scure trasversali."] whereas he was quite probably describing the apparently uncoloured spiral cordlets or the interspaces (Fig. 21). We are providing here a new series of photographs of the holotype (courtesy of MNHN) (Figs 20-22). The new pictures were taken at a different angle (VIRGINIE HÉROS, MNHN, pers. comm.) with respect to the previous ones (BOUCHET & DANRIGAL, 1982: 21, fig. 68) that showed the base less angular, the suture less canalicate and a slightly lower height, and may also have been distorted under the scanning electron micro-

scope. We agree with MIENIS (1985: 652) that the Mediterranean specimens commonly identified as *A. dorbignyi* represent a distinct species, definitely not matching the holotype of *Rissoa dorbignyi* (Fig. 19), and here ascribed to *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972 (see below).

Alvania lineata Risso, 1826 (:142, pl. IX, fig. 120) (Fig. 62) differs from *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826), by the spiral strong sculpture present on the whole teleoconch, with pointed tubercles at the intersections of spirals and axials, *vs.* the abapical half of the whorls apparently devoid of spirals with only 5 well spaced spiral cordlets on the base in *A. dorbignyi*; the axials are rounded and extend to the base *vs.* flat and interrupted in *A. dorbignyi*.

Alvania discors (Allan, 1818) (:463, pl. X, fig. 5) (Fig. 55) differs from *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826) in its multi-spiral protoconch *vs.* paucispiral in *A. dorbignyi*; the almost flat teleoconch whorls *vs.* convex in *A. dorbignyi*; the suture more neatly canalicated and the larger size.

Alvania settepassii Amati & Nofroni, 1985 (:19, 4 unnumbered figs) (Fig. 56) differs from *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826) in the flat teleoconch whorls *vs.* convex in *A. dorbignyi*; the suture non-canalicated *vs.* canalicated in *A. dorbignyi*; the axial ribs rounded, slightly to neatly prosocline *vs.* flat, orthocline or flexuose and slightly opisthocline in *A. dorbignyi*.

Alvania schwartziana Brusina, 1866 (:25, fig. 9) (Fig. 57), endemic to the east Adriatic, differs from *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826) in its lower and globose protoconch *vs.* slender, less convex and adapically shouldered in *A. dorbignyi*; in the dark-brown monochrome coloration *vs.* light brown-beige in *A. dorbignyi*; in the more marked spiral sculpture.

See also remarks under *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972, *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., *Alvania unica* n. sp. and *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. for the differences with these species.

Figures 19-22. *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1827). 19: holotype, ?Red Sea, H 2.45 mm (MNHN, SEM micrograph reproduced from BOUCHET & DANRIGAL, 1982); 20, 21: light photograph of the same specimen gold-coated for SEM; 22: idem, first whorls. Figures 23-29. *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972. 23, 24: lectotype, Haifa (Israel), H 2.8 mm (SMF); 25, 26: Šiqmônah, Haifa, (Israel), first whorls (BA); 27: paralectotype, Haifa (Israel), H 3.6 mm (SMF); 28, 29: Haifa bay (Israel), H 4 mm (M. T. Spanu collection, Alghero).

Figuras 19-22. Alvania dorbignyi (Audouin, 1827). 19: holotipo, ?Mar Rojo, H 2,45 mm (MNHN, micrografía electrónica de barrido reproducida de BOUCHET & DANRIGAL, 1982); 20, 21: fotografía del mismo ejemplar con revestimiento de oro para el MEB; 22: idem, primeras vueltas. Figuras 23-29. *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972. 23, 24: lectotipo, Haifa (Israel), H 2,8 mm (SMF); 25, 26: Šiqmônah, Haifa, (Israel), primeras vueltas (BA); 27: paralectotipo, Haifa (Israel), H 3,6 mm (SMF); 28, 29: bahía de Haifa (Israel), H 4 mm (colección M. T. Spanu, Alghero).

Alvania perversa F. Nordsieck, 1972 [new status] (Figs. 23-29)

Alvania (Alvanolira) dorbignyii perversa F. Nordsieck, 1972a: 193

Alvania (Alvanolira) perversa F. Nordsieck, 1972b: 230, fig. 14

Alvania (Alvanolira) dorbignyii perversa F. Nordsieck, 1982: 107

Alvania dorbignyi AA non *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826)

Type material: SMF 239358/1 is labelled by A. Zilch as 'Lectotypus'. "The specimen labelled as lectotype does not match the figure and is a badly preserved abraded specimen, much poorer than several of the paratype lot. Moreover, the lectotype designation is invalid because it was never published. The majority of the "paratypes" is also badly preserved." (R. JANSSEN in litt. 07.21.2014); SMF 239359/25 labelled by A. Zilch as "Paratypen". Syntype SRI ex SMF 239359, H = 2.8 mm, W = 1.8 mm (lectotype, here designated) (Figs 23, 24) (type loc.). Paralectotype (type loc.) SRI ex SMF 239359, H = 3.6 mm, W = 2.2 mm (Fig. 27), and other 24 paralectotypes (type loc.) SRI ex SMF 239359. **Other material examined:** Israel: Šiqmōnah, Haifa, 1-2 m depth, x.1998, 1 sh (BA) (Fig. 25, 26); Haifa Bay, 0-22 m depth, 32 sh (CB); Haifa, 9 m depth, 2 sh (MO); Ashdod, beach, 6 sh (CB); Soreq, 12 m depth, 2 sh (CB); Rosh Hanikrā, 3-4 m depth, 16 sh (CB); Shavey, Zion beach, 6 sh (CB); Akko, 8 m depth, 1 sh (CB); Naharyia, 0-1 m depth, 5 sh (EQ); Turkey: Bozcaada I., 5 m depth, 1 sh (EQ).

Type locality: Haifa, Israel.

Distribution: Eastern Mediterranean: Israel (this work, and BOGI & GALIL, 2006: 16, sub nomine *A. dorbignyi*), Turkey (this work), Cyprus (with unchecked records from BOGI, CIANFANELLI & TALENTI, 1988: 194; CECALUPO & QUADRI, 1996: 105, sub nomine *A. dorbignyi*) and Tunisia (CAMPANI, 2008: 1, fig. 2, sub nomine *A. dorbignyi*). Empty shells were collected in 0/22 m depth.

Description of the lectotype (Photo: S. Hof, courtesy of R. Janssen, Senckenberg Research Institute Frankfurt a. M.): Shell (Figs 23, 24) small, solid, ovate-conical, height 2.8 mm, width 1.8 mm, height aperture 1.4 mm, H/W 1.55. Protoconch paucispiral, globose, apparently devoid of sculpture.

Teloconch of 3.5 convex, almost flat whorls, suture canalculated. Axial sculpture of 12 orthocline or slightly opisthocline acute ribs on the last whorl, as wide as twice the interspaces, interrupted immediately below the suprasutural spiral cordlet.

Spiral sculpture on the last whorl of 9 (4+1+4) fine cordlets, equidistant and as wide as twice the interspaces of equal strength. Quadrangular cancellation by the intersection of axials and spirals sculptures. Apertural varix weak, no internal denticles. Columellar wall angled medially. Umbilical chink very narrow. Coloration light beige, with darker brown-orange spiral cordlets

(except the last basal one). Soft parts and operculum unknown.

Remarks: *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972 is the first name available for the species frequently identified as *Alvania dorbignyi* by several authors, not *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826), and which we consider as a distinct valid species (Figs 23-29). *Alvania dorbignyi perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972 is currently considered as taxon inquirendum (MOLLUSCABASE, 2018). *A. perversa* has commonly been considered as a small variety/subspecies of *A. dorbignyi*, due to its allegedly smaller size and the weak apertural varix (F. Nordsieck, 1972b: 230, fig. 14). However, the type material of *A. perversa* includes specimens larger than the lectotype (e.g. H = 3.6 mm, W = 2.2 mm, paralectotype) (Fig. 27). According to the examined material, *A. perversa* ranges 2.65-4.5 mm in height. The lack of denticles on the inner side of the lip in the lectotype is due to it being probably immature, since the examined material showed 7-8 weak, spaced denticles in full grown specimens. The protoconch sizes are: nucleus 0.14-0.15 mm, first half whorl diameter 0.24-0.25 mm, maximum diameter 0.35-0.40 mm, height 0.250-0.275 mm and 1.25-1.3 whorls. On the teloconch, the fourth suprasutural spiral cordlet is commonly more prominent than the others. The coloration is

rather constant: from beige to orange-brown, and the spirals always darker. It has been found sympatric with *Alvania discors* (Allan, 1818) and *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826 in Tunisia and Israel (CAMPANI, 2008: 1; Cesare Bogi, pers. comm.).

Alvania discors (Allan, 1818) (:463, pl. X, fig. 5) (Fig. 55) differs from *Alvania perversa* in its multispiral protoconch *vs.* paucispiral in *A. perversa*; the flat whorls *vs.* convex in *A. perversa*; the axials broader and flatter; the coloration different (similar only in the so variety 'feruginea'); the larger size.

Alvania settepassii Amati & Nofroni, 1985 (:19, 4 unnumbered figs) (Fig. 56) differs from *Alvania perversa* in its coloration being monochrome beige-orange *vs.* beige to brown-orange, with darker spirals (except the last basal one); the weak spirals on the last whorl *vs.* 9 fine cordlets equidistant and of equal strength in *A. perversa*; the suture non canaliculated *vs.* canaliculated in *A. perversa*.

Alvania schwartziana Brusina, 1866 (:25, fig. 9) (Fig. 57) differs from *Alvania perversa* by the almost flat whorls *vs.* convex or slightly convex; by the inner lip with 8-9 elongate, strong and close teeth *vs.* smooth or with 7-8 weak teeth widely spaced; by its monochrome dark-brown shell; by the orthocone axials *vs.* orthocone or slightly opisthocline acute ribs. It is restricted to the Adriatic Sea whilst *A. perversa* occurs in the Levantine Sea (Eastern Mediterranean Sea)

Alvania lineata Risso, 1826 (:142, pl. IX, fig. 120) (Fig. 62) differs from *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972 by its more slender and higher protoconch (300-350 μm *vs.* 250-275 μm in *A. per-*

versa); the more rounded axials, overrun by the spiral cordlets and the acute minute tubercles at the intersections. Along the Israeli coasts the two species co-occur sympatrically without any intermediate.

Alvania algeriana (Monterosato, 1877) (:34, pl. III, fig. 5) (Fig. 72) differs from *Alvania perversa* by its more slender outline, the deeper and more canaliculated suture, the spiral sculpture present only on the lower half of the whorls, of 5 robust cords, the different coloration: brown-reddish background, frequently with spirally arranged darker blotches on the spiral cords *vs.* light beige, with darker brown-orange spiral cordlets (except the last basal one) in *A. perversa*; the smaller protoconch with more whorls (d. 0.125 mm, Do 0.20 mm, nw 1.5 *vs.* d. 0.14-0.15 mm, Do 0.24-0.25 mm, nw 1.25-1.3 in *Alvania perversa*).

Alvania dorbignyi (Audouin, 1826) (:171) (Figs 19-22), for what can be desumed from the type, differs from *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972 by its protoconch more slender, less convex and with an evident adapical shoulder (lacking in *A. perversa*); the axial sculpture on the last whorl of 9 flat, orthocone (or flexuose and slightly opisthocline) ribs, as wide as the interspaces, *vs.* 12 orthocone or slightly opisthocline (never flexuose) acute ribs, as wide as twice the interspaces in *A. perversa*; the spiral sculpture barely evident, apparently lacking on the upper part of the whorls, with 5 well spaced basal cordlets *vs.* 9 fine and equidistant cordlets on the whole teleoconch in *A. perversa*.

See also remarks under *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., *Alvania unica* n. sp. and *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. for the differences with these species.

Alvania bartolinorum Amati & Smriglio n. sp. (Figs. 30-40, Table II)

Alvania garrafensis sensu AA (CAMPANI, BARTOLINI & SPANU, 2012: 85, figs 1-6; SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI, 2012: 48, 5 unnumbered figs) not *Alvania garrafensis* Peñas & Rolán, 2008.

Type material: holotype (MNHN IM-2000-27706), H 3.58 mm, W 2.16 mm. (Figs 30-32) (legit Stefano Bartolini, Florence). Paratypes: 3 sh (type loc.) (BA); 2 sh (type loc.) (CS-PM); 20 sh (type loc.) (SB-MS); 10 sh (type loc.) (AR); 5 sh (type loc.) (EQ).

Other material examined: Krk I., Croatia, 54 m depth, ix.2008, 4 sh (AR), 252 sh (SB-MS), 16 sh (EQ); Krk I., Giapni Potok, Croatia, 54 m depth, 23 sh (AR).

Type locality: Krk I., Croatia, 54 m depth.

Etymology: Dedicated to Stefano Bartolini and Maria Scaperrotta (Florence), for their kindness in making the materials from their collection always available for study, and for providing the type material.

Distribution: Basing on the examined material, it is known with certainty only from Croatia, northeastern Adriatic Sea (Krk and Prvic Islands), with empty shells collected in 40-54 m depth. A specimen from the southern Adriatic (off the Apulian coast), 101 m depth, possibly drifted from shallower habitat, has been figured (Peter Sossi at <http://www.naturamediterraneo.com/forum/topic.asp?TOPIC_ID=39830>, 29.xii.2007, as *Alvania garrafensis*). Collected in sympatry with *A. lineata* Risso, 1826 at the type locality.

Description: (between parentheses data of the holotype). Shell (Figs 30-32) small, solid, ovate-conic, height 2.84-3.96 mm (3.58 mm), width 1.75-2.28 mm (2.16 mm), H/W 1.54-1.82 (1.66). Protoconch (Figs 39, 40) paucispiral, globose, consisting of 1.3-1.6 (1.6) whorls, sculptured by partly fused and confused spiral series of granules; height 0.35-0.44 mm (0.40 mm), nucleus diameter 0.14-0.21 mm (0.19 mm), diameter of first half whorl 0.25-0.30 mm (0.275 mm), maximum diameter 0.44-0.50 mm (0.50) mm. Teleoconch of 3.3-4.1 (3.8) convex whorls, last whorl rather convex, suture impressed, canalculated. Axial sculpture on the last whorl with 12-18 (15 + v) ribs narrower than interspaces, plus the varix, orthocone on the first whorls, opisthocline and slightly sinuose on last whorl, interrupted at the periphery. Spiral sculpture starting with 2 (II, IV) cords. Last whorl with 8-11 (10) spirals non-equidistant, 4-6 (4) above the aperture, 1 at labial insertion and 3-5 (5) stronger, on the base. Spirals on last whorl slightly weaker than on previous whorls. Microsculpture on teleoconch of confused spiral microstriae and weak growth lines (Fig. 39). Umbilical chink absent or very narrow. Aperture large, ovate-squared, often flared anteriorly.

Outer lip with sharp edge, weakly varicose, with 7-9 (7) fine elongate internal denticles. Colour brown-beige with pinkish hue, first whorls often darker brown-orange, aperture often pink-violet. Rarely monochrome brown or white. Operculum and soft part unknown.

Remarks: Recently, CAMPANI, BARTOLINI & SPANU (2012: 85) and SCAPERROTTA, BARTOLINI & BOGI (2012: 48) have figured *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp. under the name *Alvania garrafensis* Peñas & Rolán, 2008. *Alvania garrafensis* (Peñas & Rolán, 2008: 21, figs 8-13) (Figs 70-72) differs in the smaller shell (H 2.8 mm *vs.* H 2.84-3.96 mm of *A. bartolinorum*), the more globose outline, the proportionally smaller aperture, the more globose apex, the first whorl with a very weak spiral sculpture and a nearly absent axial one, the orthocone axials on the other whorls with evident subsutural shoulder, the uniform light brown coloration *vs.* brown-beige with pinkish hue, with darker apex and pink-violet aperture in *A. bartolinorum*. Empty shells of *Alvania garrafensis* are collected deeper (90 m depth *vs.* 40-54 m depth of *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.).

Alvania lineata Risso, 1826 (:142, pl. IX, fig. 120) (Fig. 62) in its most common morphotype, has a stronger sculpture, especially the spirals, with marked nodules at intersections, has a monochrome background with darker spirals, a thicker varix and the axial ribs reaching the base.

Alvania schwartziana Brusina, 1866 (:25, fig. 9) (Fig. 57) differs from *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp. by its teleoconch with flat whorls *vs.* convex or slightly convex, the aperture ovate-pyriform with the external lip flat *vs.* large aperture, ovate-squared, often flared anteriorly; first whorls with obtuse profile *vs.* more acute, almost coeloconoid in *A. bartolino-*

Figures 30-40. *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp. 30-32: holotype, Krk I. (Croatia), 54 m depth, H 3.58 mm (MNHN IM-2000-27706); 33: paratype, Krk I. (Croatia), 54 m depth, H 3.3 mm (SB-MS); 34: paratype, Giapni Potok (Croatia), 54 m depth H 3.85 mm (BA); 35: paratype, Krk I., (Croatia), 54 m depth, H 3.45 mm (SB-MS); 36: paratype, Prvic Krk (Croatia), 54 m depth, H 3.45 mm (BA); 37: paratype, Giapni Potok (Croatia), 54 m depth, H 3.05 mm (BA); 38: paratype, Krk I. (Croatia), 54 m depth, H 3.05 mm (SB-MS); 39, 40: paratype, Krk I., (Croatia), SEM micrograph of the protoconch, and detail (CS-PM).

Figuras 30-40. Alvania bartolinorum n. sp. 30-32: holotipo, Isla Krk (Croacia), profundidad 54 m, H 3,58 mm (MNHN IM-2000-27706); 33: paratipo, Isla Krk (Croacia), profundidad 54 m, H 3,3 mm (SB-MS); 34: paratipo, Giapni Potok (Croacia), profundidad 54 m, H 3,85 mm (BA); 35: paratipo, Isla Krk, profundidad 54 m, H 3,45 mm (SB-MS); 36: paratipo, Prvic Krk (Croacia), profundidad 54 m, H 3,45 mm (BA); 37: paratipo, Giapni Potok, profundidad 54 m, H 3,05 mm (BA); 38: paratipo, Isla Krk, profundidad 54 m, H 3,05 mm (SB-MS); 39, 40: paratipo, Isla Krk, micrografia electrónica de barrido de la protoconch, y detalle (CS-PM).

Table II. Measurements of the protoconch and teleoconch of *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., in mm. Number 1 is the holotype. Abbreviations, h: height; d: diameter of nucleus; Do: diameter of first half whorl; DM: maximum diameter; nw: number whorls; H: height, W: width; Nw: number whorls; Nar+v: number axial ribs+ varix; Ns: numbers of spirals on the last whorl (above the aperture); Nd: number of denticles; Sts: starting number of spiral cordlets; RH/W: ratio height/width.

Protoconch	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
h	0.40	0.35	0.375	0.40	0.35	0.35	0.40	0.40	0.375	0.40	0.375	0.35
d	0.19	0.15	0.17	0.175	0.20	0.21	0.175	0.19	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.20
Do	0.275	0.275	0.25	0.29	0.325	0.29	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30
DM	0.50	0.45	0.50	0.45	0.475	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.45	0.475	0.475	0.45
nw	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.35	1.45	1.5
Teleoconch	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
H	3.58	3.05	3.3	3.45	3.6	3.2	3.5	3.4	3.4	3.7	3.65	3.15
W	2.16	1.75	2.05	1.9	2.2	1.85	2.2	2.1	2.1	2.2	2.05	1.95
RH/W	1.66	1.74	1.61	1.81	1.66	1.73	1.59	1.62	1.62	1.68	1.78	1.61
Nw	3.8	3.8	3.7	3.8	4	3.7	3.7	3.7	3.9	3.8	4	3.6
Nar+v	15+v	13+v	16+v	14+v	11+v	13+v	15+v	18+v	16+v	14+v	12+v	14+v
Ns	10(5)	8(4)	9(4)	11(6)	10(5)	9(4)	8(4)	10(5)	10(5)	10(6)	9(4)	8(4)
Nd	7	7	no	no	9	7	no	no	8	no	no	no
Sts	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

rum n. sp.; protoconch acute, paucispiral, maximum diameter 0.511 mm, sculptured by ca. 12 spirals and undulated cords (syntype MCZR) *vs.* globose, paucispiral, with maximum diameter of 0.500 mm, sculptured by partly fused and confused spiral series of granules. Colour dark-brown monochrome *vs.* brown-beige with pinkish hue, first whorls often darker brown-orange, aperture often pink-violet. Rarely monochrome brown or white.

Alvania disparilis Monterosato, 1890 (:146) (Figs 1-11) also has a globose outline, spiral and axial sculptures are both evident on the first whorls, with fine axials and spirals and quadrangular cancellation.

Alvania peloritana (Aradas & Benoit, 1874) (:205, pl IV, Fig. 16) (Figs 12-18) differs from *A. bartolinorum* n. sp. by its stronger spiral sculpture; the aperture not flared anteriorly as is generally in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.; the smaller protoconch (maximum diameter 0.40 mm *vs.* 0.44-0.50 in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.); the axial sculpture of 10 ribs on the last

whorl *vs.* 12-18 ribs in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.; the spiral sculpture of 3 spiral cords on the base *vs.* 4-6 in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.

Alvania dorbignyi (Audouin, 1827) (:171) (Figs 19-22) differs from *A. bartolinorum* n. sp. in its smaller size (H 2.45 mm *vs.* H 2.84-3.96 mm in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.); the axial ribs more robust and fewer than 10 *vs.* 12-18 in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.; the spiral sculpture weaker on the adapical part of the whorls *vs.* of same strength on the whole surface in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.

Alvania perversa F. Nordsieck, 1972 (:230, fig. 14) (Figs 23-29) differs from *A. bartolinorum* n. sp. in the different coloration (light beige background, with darker brown-orange spiral cordlets (except the last basal one) *vs.* brown-beige with pinkish hue, first whorls often darker brown-orange, aperture often pink-violet, rarely monochrome brown or white, in *A. bartolinorum* n. sp.).

See also remarks under *Alvania unica* n. sp. and *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. for the differences with these species.

Tabla II. Medidas de la protoconcha y teleoconcha de *Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp., en mm. El número 1 corresponde al holotipo. Abreviaturas, h: altura; d: diámetro del núcleo; Do: diámetro de la primera media vuelta; DM: máximo diámetro; nu: número de vueltas; H: altura, W: anchura; Nw: número de vueltas; Nar+v: número de costillas axiales + variz; Ns: número de espiras de la última vuelta (sobre la apertura); Nd: número de denticulos; Sts: número inicial de cordones espirales; RH/W: ratio altura/anchura.

13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
0.35	0.42	0.44	0.35	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.352	0.38	0.40	0.40	0.42	0.40
0.17	0.14	0.16	0.15	0.175	0.175	0.152	0.152	0.14	0.152	0.152	0.152	0.152
0.275	0.26	0.28	0.25	0.275	0.275	0.26	0.26	0.28	0.26	0.272	0.28	0.272
0.45	0.46	0.48	0.45	0.475	0.45	0.46	0.46	0.44	0.44	0.44	0.472	0.448
1.4	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.6	—	1.6	1.3	1.35	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.4
13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25
3.45	2.84	3.96	3.05	3.85	3.0	3.2	3.2	3.32	3.48	3.0	3.32	3.24
2.05	1.8	2.28	1.9	2.25	1.95	2.06	1.88	1.82	2.04	1.94	1.96	2.06
1.68	1.58	1.74	1.60	1.71	1.54	1.55	1.70	1.82	1.70	1.55	1.69	1.57
3.8	3.3	4.1	—	—	—	3.7	3.75	3.8	4	3.5	3.7	3.7
15+v	13+v	15+v	15+v	14+v	—	14+v	14+v	13+v	14+v	13+v	13+v	13+v
10(5)	9(5)	9(5)	10(5)	8(4)	9(4)	9(5)	9(5)	10(6)	11(6)	9(5)	9(5)	10(5)
no	no	no	no	8	no	9	9	no	no	7	8	no
2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Alvania unica Amati & Quaggiotto n. sp. (Figs. 41-48)

Type material: holotype (MCZR-M-22155/H), H 3.45 mm, W 2.15 mm, [paralectotype of *Alvania disparilis* Monterosato, 1890].

Type locality: Sciacca, Sicily, Italy.

Etymology: With reference to the only one specimen known.

Distribution: Known only from the holotype, Central Mediterranean: Sciacca (Sicily), unspecified depth (see also under *A. disparilis*). Possible Pleistocene (Würm) material.

Description: Shell (Figs 41-48) small, solid, ovate-conic, slightly coeloconoid, height 3.45 mm, width 2.15 mm, H/W 1.60. Protoconch (Figs 44-46, 48) paucispiral, acute, of 1.5 whorls, sculptured by ca. 10 spiral cordlets frequently interrupted and randomly fused, height 0.375 mm, diameter of nucleus 0.15 mm, diameter of first half whorl 0.25 mm, maximum diameter 0.475 mm. Teleoconch of 3.8 convex whorls, suture weakly impressed. Axial sculpture on the last whorl of 15 robust ribs plus the varix, orthocone on the first whorls, slightly sinuose on the last whorl, nar-

rower than interspaces, interrupted at the periphery. Spiral sculpture starting with 2 (II, IV) cordlets, last whorl with 11 (5, 1, 5) fine cordlets not equidistant, the three subsutural closer, those on the base more spaced and equidistant. Microsculpture not observed on the teleoconch. Umbilical chink absent. Outer lip thickened by a broad and robust varix, with 10 small internal denticles. Colour tawny, varix and aperture whitish. Operculum and soft parts unknown.

Remarks: Although based on a single specimen, this species is indisputably diagnosed by the peculiar morphology of the robust shell, with lanceolate outline slightly coeloconoid and acute spire, not corresponding to any known Recent or fossil northeastern Atlantic

species (even considering teratological specimens). Considering the sediment deposited inside the aperture, it is possible that the shell is a fossil.

Alvania disparilis Monterosato, 1890 (:146) (Figs 1-11) has a less robust shell, smaller (H 2.95 mm *vs.* H 3.45 mm in *A. unica* n. sp.), larger H/W (1.68 *vs.* 1.60 in *A. unica* n. sp.), the aperture is proportionally smaller (1.45 mm *vs.* 1.6 mm in *A. unica* n. sp.), the outline is more globose with more convex whorls, *vs.* the lanceolate/coeloconoid outline and acute spire in *A. unica* n. sp.; the protoconch is smaller (0.425 mm *vs.* 0.475 mm in *A. unica* n. sp.). The sculpture is also different: 14 fine axials, as wide as half the interspaces, and 9 (4+1+4) fine non equidistant spirals, forming quadrangular reticulate pattern and small tubercles, *vs.* 15 robust slightly sinuose axials, barely narrower than interspaces interrupted at the periphery, and 10 (5+1+4) fine spirals not equidistant; colour is with a light brown background and darker spirals and protoconch *vs.* tawny monochrome *A. unica* n. sp. with varix and aperture whitish.

Alvania claudioi Buzzurro & Landini, 2007 (:24, figs 1a-c) (Fig. 58) has a smaller shell (H 2.5-2.63 mm *vs.* H 3.45 mm of *A. unica* n. sp.), more convex whorls, finer and more numerous spirals, more evident on the base.

Alvania lanciae (Calcara, 1845) (:29, pl. IV, fig. 12) (Figs 59-61) has a globose protoconch *vs.* acute in *A. unica* n. sp.; h 0.25-0.30 mm *vs.* 0.375 mm; d 0.16-0.22 mm *vs.* 0.15 mm; Do 0.20-0.25 mm *vs.* 0.25 mm; DM 0.35-0.40 mm *vs.* 0.475 mm; of 1.25-1.3 whorls *vs.* 1.5 whorls, with an orange-skin like microsculpture of irregular pits, *vs.* ca. 10 cordlets frequently interrupted and randomly fused in *A. unica* n. sp. Teleoconch with evident microsculpture, absent in *A. unica* n. sp.

Alvania varia Tabanelli, Bongiardino & Perugia, 2011 (:46, pl. 5, figs 25-29) from the Piacenzian stage of Romagna (Pliocene), has a shorter protoconch (1.2 whorls *vs.* 1.5 in *A. unica* n. sp.), a smaller maximum diameter (0.30 mm *vs.* 0.475 mm in *A. unica* n. sp.). In *A.*

unica n. sp. the outline is slightly coeloconoid and the axial ribs are interrupted at the periphery; in *A. varia* the axial ribs are interrupted beyond the periphery, reaching the spirals of the base. *A. varia* differs by the lack of internal denticles on the outer lip, the smaller size (H 2.2 mm *vs.* H 3.45 mm in *A. unica* n. sp.) and the teleoconch microsculpture, absent in *A. unica* n. sp.

The specimens from the Pleistocene of Rhodes I. (Calabrian stage) figured as *Alvania lanciae* by CHIRLI & LINSE (2011: 61, pl 22, figs 2a-e), probably belong to a distinct species, diagnosed by a different apical sculpture (micro tubercles arranged in spirals *vs.* orange-skin microsculpture of irregular pits in *A. lanciae*); a different teleoconch sculpture, with spirals equidistant and of equal strength (*vs.* not equidistant and of varying strength in *A. lanciae*). These specimens differ from *A. unica* n. sp. in their prosocline lip with weak varix (*vs.* orthocline lip with robust varix in the new species), in the number of spiral cordlets on the last whorl (4+1+4 and equidistant *vs.* 5+1+5 and not equidistant in *A. unica* n. sp.), and in the fewer axial ribs on the last whorl (11 *vs.* 15 in *A. unica* n. sp.).

Alvania rugulosa (Aradas, 1847) (original combination: *Rissoa rugulosa* Aradas, 1847:76) [(not *Rissoa rugulosa* Hutton, 1873 = *Rissoina chathamensis* (Hutton, 1873)] fossil from Gravitelli (Messina: Plio-Pleistocene?) is the nominal taxon morphologically closest to *A. unica* n. sp. based on the original description. ARADAS (1847: 76) added that the teleoconch had 14-15 axials and 11 spirals on the last whorl, 5 on the second last, 4 on the third last. It was compared to *A. montagui* by which it would differ by being smaller, less tumid and more elongate. We have not found any type material of this taxon at either CMSN, MCZR, MBAC or MGPUF, nor have we found any topotypical shells fitting the description. We consider *Rissoa rugulosa* Aradas, 1847 as a nomen dubium. It has been synonymized with either *A. lineata* Risso, 1826 (MONTEROSATO, 1884: 59; BELLINI, 1929: 46) or

Figures 41-48. *Alvania unica* n. sp. 41, 42: holotype, Sciacca (Sicily), H 3.45 mm (MCZR-M-22155/H); 43: SEM micrograph of the holotype; 44-47: details of the protoconch; 48: original label.

Figuras 41-48. Alvania unica n. sp. 41, 42: holotipo, Sciacca (Sicilia), H 3,45 mm (MCZR-M-22155/H); 43: micrografía electrónica de barrido del holotipo; 44-47: detalles de la protoconcha; 48: etiqueta original.

with *A. montagui* (Payraudeau, 1826) (G. SEGUENZA fide L. SEGUENZA, 1903: 44).

A. bartolinorum n. sp. (Figs 30-40) differs from *A. unica* n. sp. has a non-lanceolate outline with a less acute apex, a less robust and less broad varix, a more canalized sutures, less rounded axial ribs, wider basal cords and an anteriorly flared aperture (*vs.* more rounded in *A. unica* n. sp.).

Alvania garrafensis Peñas & Rolán, 2008 (:21, figs 8-13) (Figs 73-75) differs in the smaller shell (H 2.8 mm *vs.* H 3.45 mm of *A. unica* n. sp.); the more globose outline; the first whorl with a very weak spiral sculpture and an almost absent axial one *vs.* both sculptures always well evident on all the whorls in *A. unica* n. sp.; the orthocline axial ribs on the last whorl *vs.* slightly opisthocline and sinu-

ose in *A. unica* n. sp.; the round-ovate aperture *vs.* round-ovate elongated in *A. unica* n. sp.; presence of microsculpture *vs.* absence of microsculpture in *A. unica* n. sp.; the smaller diameter of protoconch, DM 0.410 mm *vs.* DM 0.475 in *A. unica* n. sp., with more delicate sculpture and with more spiral cords, 12 *vs.* 10 in *A. unica* n. sp.

Alvania peloritana (Aradas & Benoit, 1874) (:205, pl. IV, fig. 16) (Figs 12-18) differs from *A. unica* n. sp. in its non-lanceolate outline with a less acute apex, the fewer axials on the last whorl (10 *vs.* 15), the fewer but stronger spirals on the last whorl [8 (4+1+3) *vs.* 11 (5+1+5)].

Alvania dorbigny (Audouin, 1827) (: 171) (Figs 19-22) differs from *A. unica* n. sp. in its smaller size (H 2.45 mm *vs.* H 3.45 mm), the higher H/W ratio (1.81 *vs.*

Figures 49-54. *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. 49, 50: holotype, Zara (now Zadar, Croatia), H 2.6 mm (MCZR-M-22152/H); 51: original label; 52: SEM micrograph of the holotype; 53, 54: details of the protoconch and first teleoconch whorl.

Figuras 49-54. Alvania zaraensis n. sp. 49, 50: holotipo, Zara (ahora Zadar, Croacia), H 2,6 mm (MCZR-M-22152/H); 51: etiqueta original; 52: micrografía electrónica de barrido del holotipo; 53, 54: detalles de la protoconcha y primera vuelta de teleoconcha.

1.60), the fewer axials on the last whorl (10 vs. 15), the weaker spiral sculpture (on the last whorl 5 well spaced spiral cordlets on the base and one more prominent suprasutural, the upper part of the whorl apparently devoid of spirals vs. 11 spiral cordlets on the last whorls in *A. unica* n. sp.).

Alvania perversa Nordsieck F., 1972 (: 230, fig. 14) (Figs 23-29) differs from *A. unica* n. sp. by the less convex whorls and the more canaliculated suture, the

fewer axials on the last whorl (12 vs. 15), and fewer spirals on the last whorl [9 (4+1+4) equidistant vs. 11 (5+1+5) non-equidistant], the different chromatic pattern (light beige background, with darker brown-orange spiral cordlets (except the last basal one) vs. tawny background, with whitish varix and aperture in *A. unica* n. sp.).

See also remarks under *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. for the differences with this species.

Alvania zaraensis Amati & Appolloni n. sp. (Figs. 49-54, Table III)

Type material: holotype (MCZR-M-22152/H), (H 2.6 mm, W 1.6 mm) and 14 paratypes (MCZR-M-22152/P), (type loc.).

Type locality: Zara [now Zadar], Croatia.

Etymology: From the type locality, Zara.

Table III. Measurements of the protoconch and teleoconch of *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp., in mm. Number 1 is the holotype. Abbreviations, h: height; d: diameter of nucleus; Do: diameter of first half whorl; DM: maximum diameter; nw: number whorls; H: height, W: width; RH/W: ratio height/width; Nw: number of teleoconch whorls; Nar+v: number axial ribs+ varix; Ns: number of spirals on the last whorl (above the aperture); Nd: number of denticles; Sts: starting number of spiral cordlets.

Tabla III. Medidas de la protoconcha y teleoconcha de *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp., en mm. El número 1 corresponde al holotipo. Abreviaturas, h: altura; d: diámetro del núcleo; Do: diámetro de la primera media vuelta; DM: máximo diámetro; nw: número de vueltas; H: altura, W: anchura; RH/W: ratio alturanchura; Nw: número de vueltas de la teleoconcha; Nar+v: número de costillas axiales + variz; Ns: número de espiras de la última vuelta (sobre la apertura); Nd: número de denticulos; Sts: número inicial de cordones espirales.

Protoconch	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
h	0.30	0.35	0.25	—	0.30	—	0.30	—	0.30	0.31	0.30	0.31
d	0.137	0.14	0.14	—	0.175	0.14	0.125	—	0.15	0.145	0.14	0.125
Do	0.237	0.225	0.225	—	0.225	0.225	0.20	—	0.275	0.245	0.26	0.225
DM	0.356	0.35	0.34	—	0.365	—	0.325	—	0.36	0.365	0.375	0.35
nw	1.25	1.35	1.3	—	1.35	—	1.3	—	1.35	1.35	1.4	1.3
Teleoconch	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
H	2.6	2.6	2.9	2.95	2.75	2.7	2.75	2.5	2.9	2.75	2.75	2.1
W	1.6	1.65	1.8	1.9	1.77	1.8	1.7	1.57	1.75	1.77	1.75	1.45
RH/W	1.62	1.57	1.61	1.55	1.55	1.50	1.62	1.59	1.66	1.55	1.57	1.45
Nw	4	4	4.8	4.8	4.6	4.6	4.6	4	4.8	4.6	4.6	3.7
Nar+v	9+v	11+v	10+v	10+v	9+v	10+v	11+v	12+v	10+v	11+v	9+v	10+v
Ns	9(4)	8(4)	9(4)	9(4)	9(4)	9(4)	10(4)	9(4)	10(4)	10(4)	8(4)	9(4)
Nd	7	no	8	8	8	no	7	8	8	8	8	7
Sts	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Distribution: Mediterranean: Adriatic Sea, Zara [now Zadar] (Croatia), unspecified depth; habitat unknown, it is presumed alive in algal facies.

Description: (between parentheses data of the holotype). Shell (Figs 49-54) small, solid, ovate-conic, height 2.10–2.95 mm (2.6 mm), width 1.45–1.9 mm (1.6 mm), H/W 1.45–1.66 (1.62). Protoconch (Figs 53, 54) paucispiral, slightly globose, shiny, without apparent sculpture under SEM due to the worn condition of the specimen, of 1.25–1.4 (1.25) whorls, height 0.25–0.35 mm (0.30 mm), diameter of nucleus 0.125–0.175 mm (0.137 mm), diameter of first half whorl 0.20–0.275 mm (0.237), maximum diameter 0.325–0.375 mm (0.356 mm). Teleoconch of 3.7–4.8 (4) barely convex whorls, suture deep and

canaliculated. Axial sculpture of 9–12+v (9+v) strong orthocone ribs, as wide as the interspaces, interrupted at the periphery, in correspondence with the sutural cordlet. Spiral sculpture starting with 2 (II, IV) weak cordlets. Last whorl with 8–10 (9) spirals; the adapical 4 above the aperture, equidistant and as wide as the interspaces, the basal 4–6 (5) (including the sutural one) finer and more spaced; fourth adapical cordlet more pronounced. Rounded tubercles at the intersections. Microsculpture absent. Umbilical chink barely visible. Outer lip thickened by a broad and robust varix, with 7–8 (7) internal elongate denticles. Colour monochrome light beige-orange, rarely light brown with whitish supra-sutural band. Varix whitish with weak orange lines in correspondence with the

spirals. Operculum and soft parts unknown.

Remarks: A vial in the Monterosato collection (MCZR-M-22152) contains 32 shells from Zara (now Zadar, Croatia), labelled (Fig. 51) “Alvania montagui xxxxx [unreadable] di Zara”, of which 7 *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826, 10 *Alvania lanciae* (Calcara, 1845) and 15 *Alvania zaraensis* n. sp. Actually, the new species resembles a dwarf form of *Alvania discors* (Allan, 1818) (:463, pl X, fig. 5) (Fig. 55), but the latter has a multispiral protoconch of 1.7-1.8 whorls vs. 1.25-1.4 of *A. zaraensis* n. sp., with the diameter of nucleus 0.85-0.112 mm vs. 0.125-0.175 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.; the shell is then larger (> 5 mm vs. < 3 mm in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.) and more brightly coloured and more polychrome.

Alvania bozcaadensis Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013 (:164, figs 1-8, 9-11, 28-29) (Figs 61, 62) is probably the morpholog-

ically closest species, differing by the more slender outline, the more globose apex, the more numerous and finer axial ribs on last whorl (13-16 vs. 9-12 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.), as wide as half the interspaces vs. larger than interspaces in *A. zaraensis* n. sp., the more globose apex, often with lower number of whorls (1.25 vs. 1.25-1.40 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.), and a smaller nucleus (0.100 mm vs. 0.125-0.175 mm in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.).

Alvania lanciae (Calcara, 1845) (:29, pl. IV, fig. 12) (Figs 59-61) is similar to the new species in particular with some of its Central Mediterranean morphs (AMATI, 2012: 118-119 pls 1-2, figs A-G; A-F) with robust shell and almost flat whorls; it differs by the evident teleoconch and protoconch microsculptures, absent in *A. zaraensis* n. sp., and for the more globose protoconch. (AMATI & OLIVERIO, 1987: 51, 52, pl. II, fig. 5 and

(Right page) Figures 55-70. *Alvania* spp. 55: *Alvania discors* (Allan, 1818), Sant’Agostino, Civitavecchia (Italy), H 5 mm (BA); 56: *Alvania settepassii* Amati & Nofroni, 1985, paratype, Torrevadalliga, Civitavecchia (Italy), 25-30 m depth, H 4.3 mm (BA); 57: *Alvania schwartziana* Brusina, 1866, Pago (now Pag, Croatia), H 3.6 mm (BA); 58: *Alvania claudioi* Buzzurro & Landini, 2007, Zannone I. (Italy), H 2.5 mm, (BA); 59: *Alvania lanciae* (Calcara, 1845), Cala Gonone (Sardinia), 0.5 m depth, H 3.25 mm, (BA); 60: *Alvania lanciae* (Calcara, 1845), Bastia, Corsica (France), H 3.45 mm (MCZR-M-22161); 61: *Alvania lanciae* (Calcara, 1845), Elba I. (Italy), H 3.58 mm (AN); 62: *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826, Salina I. (Sicily), H 3.65 mm (BA); 63, 64: *Alvania bozcaadensis* Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013, Aydıncik (Turkey), H 2.15 mm (BA); 65, 66: *Alvania campanii* Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013, Bozcaada (Turkey), 8 m depth H 2.55 mm (BA); 67: *Alvania aeoliae* Palazzi, 1988, Salina I. (Sicily), H 2.3 mm (BA); 68, 69: *Alvania datchaensis* Amati & Oliverio, 1987, Aydıncik (Turkey), H 2.4 mm (BA); 70, 71: *Alvania fractospira* Oberling, 1970, Trogyr (Croatia), H 2.55 mm (BA); 72: *Alvania algeriana* (Monterosato, 1877) Algiers (Algeria), H 2.95 mm (MCZR-M-22182).

(Página derecha) Figuras 55-70. *Alvania* spp. 55: *Alvania discors* (Allan, 1818), Sant’Agostino, Civitavecchia (Italia), H 5 mm (BA); 56: *Alvania settepassii* Amati y Nofroni, 1985, paratipo, Torrevadalliga, Civitavecchia (Italia), profundidad 25-30 m, H 4,3 mm (BA); 57: *Alvania schwartziana* Brusina, 1866, Pago, (now Pag, Croacia), H 3,6 mm (BA); 58: *Alvania claudioi* Buzzurro & Landini, 2007, Zannone I. (Italia), H 2,5 mm, (BA); 59: *Alvania lanciae* (Calcara, 1845), Cala Gonone (Cerdeña), profundidad 0,5 m, H 3,25 mm, (BA); 60: *Alvania lanciae*, Bastia, Córcega (Francia), H 3,45 mm (MCZR-M-22161); 61: *Alvania lanciae*, Elba I. (Italia), H 3,58 mm (AN); 62: *Alvania lineata* Risso, 1826, Salina I. (Sicilia), H 3,65 mm (BA); 63, 64: *Alvania bozcaadensis* Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013, Aydıncik (Turquía), H 2,15 mm (BA); 65, 66: *Alvania campanii* Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013, Bozcaada (Turquía), profundidad 8 m, H 2,55 mm (BA); 67: *Alvania aeoliae* Palazzi, 1988, Salina I. (Sicilia), H 2,3 mm (BA); 68, 69: *Alvania datchaensis* Amati & Oliverio, 1987, Aydıncik (Turquía), H 2,4 mm (BA); 70, 71: *Alvania fractospira* Oberling, 1970, Trogyr (Croacia), H 2,55 mm (BA); 72: *Alvania algeriana* (Monterosato, 1877) Argel (Argelia), H 2,95 mm (MCZR-M-22182).

Figures 73-82. *Alvania* spp. 73: *Alvania garrafensis* Peñas & Rolán, 2008: SEM micrograph of the holotype, Mar de Cubelles, Garraf (Spain), H 2.8 mm (MNCN); 74: Detail of the protoconch; 75: Detail of the teleoconch; 76: *Alvania colossophilus* Oberling, 1970, Capo Greco Protaras, Cyprus, H 3.75 mm (BA); 77: *Alvania aspera* (Philippi, 1844), Portoroz (Slovenia), H 3 mm (BA); 78: *Alvania elisae* Margelli, 2001, paratype, Capraia I. (Italy), H 3.75 mm (CS-PM); 79: *Alvania elisae* Margelli, 2001, Capri I. (Italy), H 3.6 mm (MCZR-M-30060), intermediate specimen, tending to species *A. settepassii*; 80: *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1827), reproduced from SAVIGNY, 1817: pl. 3, 22; 81: *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1827), reproduced from NORDSIECK, 1972: 230, 13; 82: *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972, reproduced from NORDSIECK, 1972: 230, 14.

Figuras 73-82. Alvania spp. 73: *Alvania garrafensis* Peñas & Rolán, 2008: *micrografía electrónica de barrido del holotipo, Mar de Cubelles, Garraf (España), H 2,8 mm (MNCN)*; 74: *Detalle de la protoconcha*; 75: *Detalle de la teleoconcha*; 76: *Alvania colossophilus* Oberling, 1970, *Capo Greco Protaras, Chipre, H 3,75 mm (BA)*; 77: *Alvania aspera* (Philippi, 1844), *Portoroz (Eslovenia), H 3 mm (BA)*; 78: *Alvania elisae* Margelli, 2001, *paratipo, isla de Capraia (Italia), H 3,75 mm (CS-PM)*; 79: *Alvania elisae* Margelli, 2001, *isla de Capri (Italia), H 3,6 mm (MCZR-M-30060), ejemplar intermedio, que tiende hacia la especie A. settepassii*; 80: *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1827), *reproducido de SAVIGNY, 1817: pl. 3, 22*; 81: *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1827), *reproducido de NORDSIECK, 1972: 230, 13*; 82: *Alvania perversa* F. Nordsieck, 1972, *reproducido de NORDSIECK, 1972: 230, 14*.

Figures 83-88. *Alvania montagui* (Payraudeau, 1826). 83, 84: syntype in apertural and dorsal view, Corsica, H 4.2 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-27921); 85: syntype in apertural view, Corsica, H 3.95 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-27921); 86, 87: SEM micrograph of the same syntype as 83, 84, in apertural view (86) and detail of the first whorls (87); 88: original figure (reproduced from PAYRAUDEAU, 1826: pl. V, fig 13; drawing tipped).

Figuras 83-88. Alvania montagui (Payraudeau, 1826). 83, 84: sintipo en vista apertural y dorsal, Córcega, H 4,2 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-27921); 85: sintipo en vista apertural, Córcega, H 3,95 mm (MNHN-IM-2000-27921); 86, 87: micrografía electrónica de barrido del mismo sintipo que el 83, 84, en vista apertural (86) y detalle de las primeras vueltas (87); 88: figura original (reproducida de PAYRAUDEAU, 1826: pl. V, fig. 13; dibujo volcado).

pl. III, figs 6,7; AMATI, 2012: 120, fig. 3, A, B; TISSELLI & GIUNCHI, 2013: 169, pl. 2, figs 12-14).

Alvania campanii Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013 (:165, figs 15-21, 26-27, 31-32, 36) (Figs 63, 64) has finer axials as wide as half the interspaces *vs.* robust barely larger than interspaces ribs in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.; its varix is less robust; the protoconch is more globose, and sculptured by granules set in series of 12-14 slightly

wavy spiral threads *vs.* smooth in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.

Alvania elisae Margelli, 2001 (:43, figs 1-11, 16-19, pls 1-3) (Figs 78, 79) differs in the larger shell (H 3.5-4 mm *vs.* H 2.1-2.95 mm in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.), the protoconch has an evident microsculptures *vs.* absent in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.; a greater number of axial ribs on the last whorl 15-16 *vs.* 9-12 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.

Alvania disparilis Monterosato, 1890 (:146) (Figs 1-11) has a less robust shell with more convex whorls, finer and more numerous axial ribs (14-15 *vs.* 9-12 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.).

Alvania peloritana (Aradas & Benoit, 1874) (:205, pl. IV, fig. 16) (Figs 12-18) has more convex whorls *vs.* almost flat in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.; less incise suture *vs.* deeply canaliculate in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.; axial ribs extending beyond the periphery *vs.* interrupted at the periphery in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.; larger size (3.0-3.35 *vs.* 2.1-2.95 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.).

Alvania dorbignyi (Audouin, 1827) (:171) (Figs 19-22) has a higher H/W ratio (1.81 *vs.* 1.45-1.66 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.); opisthocline flexuose axials *vs.* orthocline in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.

Alvania perversa F. Nordsieck, 1972 (:230, fig. 14) (Figs 23-29) differs in its weaker sculpture (both axial and spiral), with axials less elevate.

Alvania bartolinorum n. sp. (Figs 30-40) differs in its shell less robust and thick, with weaker sculpture (both axial and spiral), especially the spiral one, and in the maximum diameter of the protoconch (0.44-0.50 mm *vs.* 0.325-0.375 mm *A. zaraensis* n. sp.).

Alvania unica n. sp. (Figs 41-48) differs in the larger size (height 3.45 mm *vs.* 2.10-2.95 mm in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.), the finer and more numerous axials (15 *vs.* 9-12 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.), the suture less canaliculate, the more numerous inner denticles on the outer lip (10 *vs.* 7-8 in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.), the higher protoconch, with more whorls and wider diameter (nw 1.5, h 0.375 mm, DM 0.475 mm *vs.* nw 1.25-1.4, h 0.25-0.35 mm, DM 0.325-0.375 mm in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.), the protoconch sculpture of c. 10 spiral cordlets, apparently lacking in *A. zaraensis* n. sp.

Specimens from some localities of the eastern Mediterranean – Greece: Crete, beached bioclastic sand, 2 sh (RP); Saronikos, 1 sh (EQ); Turkey: Taşucu, 5 sh (EQ); Iskenderum Gulf, 2 sh (EQ); Bozcaada I. 3 sh (EQ) – are very similar to typical *A. zaraensis* n. sp. The shells are often larger at the same number of whorls, the height/width ratio is higher, the tubercles at the intersections are more rounded; the colour is yellowish with two white suprasutural cords, and the basal cords are dashed with darker colour and the columella is darker. We consider this material worthy of a deeper insight for these potentially diagnostic characters.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Virginie Héros and Philippe Maestrati (MNHN, Paris) and Monica Leonardi (CMSN, Milan) are thanked for their very kind collaboration with type material searches; Manuel Caballer (project e-Recolnat; MNHN, Paris) for the pictures of the holotype of *Alvania dorbignyi* and of the syntypes of *Alvania montagui*; Ronald Janssen and S. Hof (SRI, Frankfurt am Main) for the pictures of the type material of *Alvania perversa*; Paul Mazza (MGPU, Florence) for his assistance during our visits to examine Seguenza's material; Emilio Rolán (Vigo) for the pictures (SEM) of the holotype of *Alvania garrafensis*; Andrea Nappo (Quartu Sant'Elena) for the photo of Fig. 61. A sincere thank to

Andrea Di Giulio (Dipartimento di Scienze, "Roma Tre" University, Rome) for the SEM photos, carried out at LIME (Interdepartmental Laboratory of Electron Microscopy, "Roma Tre" University, Rome); Danilo Scuderi (Catania), Italo Nofroni (Rome), Cesare Bogi (Livorno), Stefano Bartolini and Maria Scaperotta (Florence), Alessandro Raveggi (Florence) Raffaele Petrone (Rome) and Attilio Pagli (Vinci, Florence) for their friendly help with discussions and materials. The authors are grateful to Serge Gofas (Departamento de Biología Animal, Universidad de Málaga, Spain) and to an anonymous reviewer, for the useful comments that helped to improve this article.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AARTSEN VAN J.J. 1982. Tavole sinottiche di conchiologia Mediterranea ed Europea (Gen. *Alvania*). *La Conchiglia*, 16 (158–159): 4–5.
- ALBANO P. G. & SABELLI B. 2009. *I Molluschi delle Secche di Tor Paterno*. Collana: Gli Studi e le Guide di RomaNatura. 2. Ente Regionale RomaNatura, Roma, 95 pp.
- ALLAN T. 1818. Sketch of the Geology of the Environs of Nice. *Transactions of the Royal Society of Edimburgh*, 8: 427–464.
- AMATI B. 2012. *Alvania consociella* Monterosato, 1884 junior synonym of *Alvania lanciae* (Calcare, 1845) (Prosobranchia, Rissoidae). *Bollettino Malacologico*, 48: 116–121.
- AMATI B. & NOFRONI I. 1985. *Alvania settepassii* sp. n. (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia). *Notiziario del C.I.S.Ma.*, 6 (1–2): 19–27 [1984].
- AMATI B. & OLIVERIO M. 1987. *Alvania datchaensis* sp. n. (Gastropoda; Prosobranchia). *Notiziario del C.I.S.Ma.*, 9 (10): 46–53.
- APPOLLONI M., SMRIGLIO C., AMATI B., LUGLIÈ L., NOFRONI I., TRINGALI L. P., MARIOTTINI P. & OLIVERIO M. 2018. Catalogue of the primary types of marine molluscan taxa described by Tommaso Allery Di Maria, Marquis of Monterosato, deposited in the Museo Civico di Zoologia, Roma. *Zootaxa*, 4477 (1): 1–138
- ARADAS A. 1847. Descrizione delle conchiglie fossili di Gravitelli presso Messina. *Atti dell'Accademia Gioenia di Scienze Naturali*. Ser. II, 3: 57–88.
- ARADAS A. & BENOIT L. 1872–1876. Conchigliologia vivente marina della Sicilia e delle isole che la circondano 1–3. *Atti dell'Accademia Gioenia di Scienze Naturali*, 8: 113–226, pls 3–4 (1874).
- AUDOIN J.V. 1826. Explication sommaire des planches de Mollusques de l'Égypte et de la Syrie publiés par J.C. Savigny. In Savigny J.C. Description de l'Égypte ou recueil des observations et des recherches qui ont été faites en Égypte pendant l'expédition de l'armée française, publié par C.L.F. Panckoucke. Seconde édition, *Histoire Naturelle Zoologie Animaux Invertébrés*, 22: 117–212
- ÁVILA C.M. S.P. 2005. *Processos e padrões de dispersão e colonização nos Rissoidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) dos Açores. Tese de Doutoramento*, Universidade dos Açores, Ponta Delgada. 329 pp.
- ÁVILA C.M. S.P., GOUD J. & FRIAS MARTINS (DE) A.M. 2012. Patterns of Diversity of the Rissoidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda) in the Atlantic and the Mediterranean Region. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2012, Article ID 164890, 30 pp, 2012. doi:10.1100/2012/164890.
- BARASH A. & DANIN Z. 1992. *Annotated list of Mediterranean Molluscs of Israel and Sinai. Fauna Palestina. Mollusca I*. The Israeli Academy of sciences and Humanities. 405 pp, 372 figs.
- BELLINI R. 1929. I molluschi del golfo di Napoli (Studi precedenti, l'ambiente, enumerazione e sininimia). *Annuario del Museo della R. Università di Napoli* (N. Ser.) 6 (2): 87 pp.
- BOGI C. & GALIL B. S. 2006. Nuovi ritrovamenti lungo le coste Israeliane. *Notiziario S.I.M.* 24 (5–8): 16–18.
- BOGI C., CIANFANELLI S. & TALENTI E. 1988. Contributo alla conoscenza della malacofauna dell'isola di Cipro. In (Nofroni I. ed.) *Atti della prima giornata di studi malacologici del C.I.S.Ma.* pp 187–214.
- BOUCHET P. & DANRIGAL F. 1982. Napoleon's Egyptian campaign (1798–1801) and the Savigny collection of shells. *The Nautilus*. 96 (1): 9–24.
- BRUSINA S. 1866. Contribuzione pella fauna dei Molluschi dalmati. *Edito per cura dell'Imperiale e Reale Società Zoologico-Botanica di Vienna*, 134 pp.
- BUZZURRO G. & LANDINI F. 2007. Descrizione di una nuova specie di Rissoidae (Gastropoda: Prosobranchia) per le coste laziali (Mar Tirreno). *Bollettino Malacologico*, 42 (1–4):24–26.
- CALCARA P. 1845. *Cenno sui Molluschi viventi e fossili della Sicilia da servire di supplimento ed insieme di critiche osservazioni all'opera di R. A. Philippi*. Reale Stamperia e Libreria, Palermo, pp. 1–65, [1–2], pls I–IV.
- CAMPANI E. 2008. An odd finding of *Alvania dorbignyi* (Gastropoda: Rissoidae). *Marine Biodiversity Records*, 2: E31. doi:10.1017/S1755267208000353
- CAMPANI E., BARTOLINI S. & SPANU M.T. 2012. *Alvania garrafensis* Penas & Rolan, 2008 (Gastropoda: Rissoidae) from Croatian water. *Iberus*, 30 (1): 85–89.
- CECALUPO A. & QUADRI P. 1996. Contributo alla conoscenza malacologica per il Nord dell'isola di Cipro (Parte II). *Bollettino Malacologico*, 30 (10–12): 269–276.
- CHIRLI C. & LINSE U. 2011. *The Pleistocene Marine Gastropods of the Rhodes Island (Greece)*. Grafiche PDB, Tavarnelle V.P. (Firenze), 447 pp.
- CRISCIONE F. & PONDER W.F. 2013. A phylogenetic analysis of rissooidean and cingulopsoidean families (Gastropoda: Caenogastropoa). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, 66: 1075– 1082.

- CRISCIONE F., PONDER W.F., KOHLER F., TAKANO T. & KANO Y. 2016. A molecular phylogeny of Rissoidae (Caenogastropoda: Rissoidae) allows testing the diagnostic utility of morphological traits. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 179: 23–40.
- DE GREGORIO A. 1889a. Esami di taluni Molluschi viventi e terziari del Bacino Mediterraneo. *Il Naturalista Siciliano* 8 (10–11): 248–256.
- DE GREGORIO A. 1889b. Iconografia conchiologica mediterranea vivente e terziaria. I. Studi sul genere *Scalaria*: 1–10, Tav. I. *Annales de Géologie et de Paléontologie*. Palermo, Libreria internazionale L. Pedone Lauriel di Carlo Clausen.
- DEKKER H. & ORLIN Z. 2000. Check list of Red Sea Mollusca. *Spirula*, 47 (supplement), 1–46.
- DELONGUEVILLE C. & SCAILLET R. 2007. Les espèces invasives de mollusques en Méditerranée. *Novapex*, 8 (2): 47–70.
- GOFAS S. & ZENETOS A. 2003. Exotic molluscs in the Mediterranean basin: current status and perspectives. *Oceanography and Marine Biology: an Annual Review*, 41: 237–277.
- GOFAS S., MORENO D. & SALAS C. 2011. *Molluscos marinos de Andalucía*. Universidad de Malaga servicio de Publicaciones e Intercambio Científico. Malaga, Vol.1, 342 pp.
- GRANATA-GRILLO G. 1877. Contribuzione pella Fauna dei Molluschi del Mediterraneo. Catalogo delle Conchiglie di Messina e dintorni. *Il Barth*, 4: 143–147.
- GRAY J.E. 1847. A list of the genera of Recent Mollusca, their synonyma and types. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London 1847*: 129–242.
- HADLEY A. 2006. Combine ZP public domain image processing software. Available from <https://web.archive.org/web/20160221032141/http://www.hadleyweb.pwp.blueyonder.co.uk/>
- HORNUNG A. & MERMOD G. 1927. Mollusques de la Mer Rouge recueillis par A. Issel faisant partie des collections du Musée Civique d'Histoire Naturelle de Gênes. Quatrième partie, Rissoidés. *Annali del Museo Civico di Storia Naturale Giacomo Doria*, Genova, 52 (IV parte): 363–372.
- ICZN [International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature] 1999. International code of zoological nomenclature, Fourth edition. London: International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature. London, xxix + 306 pp.
- ISSEL A. 1869. *Malacologia del Mar Rosso ricerche zoologiche e paleontologiche. Memoria letta al congresso dei Naturalisti Italiani in Vicenza nel 1868*. Pisa, Editori della biblioteca malacologica. 387 pp.
- JANSSEN R., ZUSCHIN M. & BAAL C. 2011. Gastropods and their habitats from the northern Red Sea (Egypt: Safaga) Part 2: Caenogastropoda: Sorbeoconcha and Littorinimorpha. *Annalen des Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien, Serie A*, 113: 373–509, Wien.
- MARGELLI A. 2001. A new species from Capraia Is. (Tuscan Archipelago): *Alvania elisae* sp. nov.. *La Conchiglia* 300: 43–50.
- MARÍN A. & ROS J. 1987. Catalogo preliminar de los gasteropodos marinos del sudeste español. *Iberus*, 7(1): 137–145.
- MIENIS H.K. 1985. Is *Alvania dorbignyi* (Audouin, 1826) a Lessepsian migrant? *Levantina*, 59, 652–654.
- MIENIS H.K. 2005. Mariene mollusken uit het oostelijk deel van de middellandse zee 25. De CIESM-atlas van exotische mollusken in de Middellandse Zee en nogmaals iets over de status van *Alvania dorbigny*. *Spirula*, 345: 104–105.
- MOAZZO P.G. 1939. *Mollusques testacés marins du Canal de Suez. Mémoires de l'Institut d'Égypte*, 38, 1–287.
- MOLLUSCABASE 2018. *Alvania dorbignyi perversa* Nordsieck, 1972 †. Accessed at: <http://www.molluscabase.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=873410> on 2018-04-30).
- MONTEROSATO T.A. 1872. Notizie intorno alle conchiglie Mediterranee. *Ufficio Tipografico M. Amenta*, Palermo, p. 15–61.
- MONTEROSATO T.A. 1875. Nuova rivista delle conchiglie mediterranee. *Atti dell'Accademia di Scienze e Lettere*, Palermo, 2: 1–50.
- MONTEROSATO T.A. 1878. Enumerazione e sinonimia delle conchiglie mediterranee. *Giornale Scienze Naturali ed Economiche*, Palermo, 13: 61–115.
- MONTEROSATO T.A. 1884. *Nomenclatura generica e specifica di alcune conchiglie mediterranee*. Stabilimento Tipografico Virzi. Palermo. 152 pp.
- MONTEROSATO T.A. 1890. Conchiglie della profondità del mare di Palermo. *Naturalista Siciliano*, 9 (6): 140–151; 9 (7): 157–166; 9 (8): 181–191.
- NEVILL G. 1885. *Hand lists of Mollusca in the Indian Museum, Calcutta, Part II. GASTROPODA. Prosobranchia-Neurobranchia (contd.)*. Calcutta: Printed by order of the trustees. pp. 306.
- NEWTON R.S. & STEFANON A. 1975. The “Tegnue de Ciosa” area: patch reefs in the northern Adriatic Sea. *Marine Geology*, 19: M27–M33.
- NORDSIECK F. 1972a. *Die europäischen Meeresschnecken (Opisthobranchia mit Pyramidellidae; Rissioacea). Vom Eismeer bis Kapverden, Mittelmeer und Schwarzes Meer*. Gustav Fischer, Stuttgart XIII + 327 pp.

- NORDSIECK F. 1972b. Marine Gastropoden aus der Shiqmona-Bucht in Israel. *Archiv für Molluskenkunde* 102(4–6): 227–245.
- NORDSIECK F. 1982. *Die Europäischen Meeres-Gehäuseschnecken (Prosobranchia). Vom Eismeer bis Kapverden, Mittelmeer und Schwarzes Meer. 2., Völlig Neubearbeitete und Erweiterte Auflage.* Gustav Fischer Verlag, Stuttgart, xii + 539 pp.
- ÖBERLING J.J. 1970. Quelques espèces nouvelles de Gastéropodes du bassin Méditerranéen. *Kleine Mitteilungen, Naturhistorisches Museum Bern*, 1: 1–7.
- ÖZTÜRK B., BUZZURRO G. & AVNI BENLI H. 2004. Marine molluscs from Cyprus: new data and checklist. *Bollettino Malacologico*, 39 (5–8): 49–78.
- PALAZZI S. 1997. Un problema ancora... spinoso. I Rissoidi del Mediterraneo. *La Conchiglia*, Roma. 29 (285): 35–40.
- PALLARY P. 1926. Explication des planches de J. C. Savigny. *Mémoires de l'Institut d'Égypte*, 11: I–VII, 1–138.
- PAYRAUDEAU B.C. 1826. *Catalogue descriptif et méthodique des annélides et des mollusques de l'île de Corse*, 218 pp, 8 pls. Paris.
- PEÑAS A., ROLÁN E. & BALLESTEROS M. 2008. Segunda adición a la fauna malacológica del litoral del Garraf (NE de la Península Ibérica). *Iberus*, 26 (2): 15–42.
- PONDER W.F. 1985. *A Review of the Genera of the Rissoidae (Mollusca: Mesogastropoda: Rissoacea)*. Records of the Australian Museum. Supplement 4: 1–221 [1984].
- RISSO A. 1826. *Histoire naturelle des principales productions l'Europe Méridionale et particulièrement de celles des environs de Nice et des Alpes Maritimes*. Paris, Levrault, libraire 4: 439 pp.
- SAVIGNY J.C. 1817. Description de l'Égypte, ou recueil des observations et des recherches qui ont été faites en Égypte pendant l'expédition de l'armée française, publié par ordre du Gouvernement. *Histoire Naturelle, Planches, Vol II*. Paris: de l'Imprimerie Royale.
- SCAPERROTTA M., BARTOLINI S. & BOGI C. 2012. *Accrescimenti. Stadi di accrescimento dei molluschi marini del Mediterraneo*. Volume IV, 184 pp.
- SCUDERI D. 2007. The recent discovery of a new section of the malacological collection of Andrea Aradas. IV International Congress of the European Malacological Societies, October 10–14, 2005 - Naples (Italy). *Bollettino Malacologico*, 43: 125–129.
- SCUDERI D. & AMATI B. 2012. Rediscovery and re-evaluation of a “ghost” taxon: the case of *Rissoa galvagni* Aradas et Maggiore, 1844 (Caenogastropoda Rissoidae). *Biodiversity Journal*, 3 (4): 511–520.
- SCUDERI D. & TERLIZZI A. 2012. *Manuale di Malacologia dell'Alto Jonio*. Grifo Ed., 188 pp.
- SEGUENZA L. 1903. Rissoidi Neogenici della provincia di Messina. *Palaeontographia Italica*, 9: 36–60 [reprint paginated 1–26].
- TABANELLI C., BONGIARDINO C. & PERUGIA I. 2011. Cingulopsidae e Rissoidae pliocenici provenienti dallo “spungone” (Pedeappennino romagnolo) e loro eventuale significato paleoambientale (Gastropoda Caenogastropoda Cingulopsidae, Rissoidae). *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*, 32: 27–76.
- TISSELLI M. & GIUNCHI L. 2013. Due nuove specie di *Alvania* (Gastropoda: Rissoidae) dal nord- ovest della Turchia. (Gastropoda Caenogastropoda Rissoidae). *Quaderno di Studi e Notizie di Storia Naturale della Romagna*, 37: 163–174.
- VILLARI A. & SCUDERI D. 2017. Taxonomical notes on some poorly known mollusca species from the Strait of Messina (Italy). *Biodiversity Journal*, 8 (1): 193–204.
- ZENETOS A., GOFAS S., RUSSO G. & TEMPLADO J. 2004. *CIESM Atlas of exotic species in the Mediterranean*. Vol. 3. Molluscs (ed. F. Briand). Monaco: CIESM.

APPENDIX. LIST OF MATERIAL EXAMINED

- Alvania bartolinorum* n. sp. (See under species heading);
Alvania unica n. sp. (See under species heading);
Alvania zaraensis n. sp. (See under species heading);
Alvania disparilis Monterosato, 1890 (See under species heading);
Alvania peloritana (Aradas & Benoit, 1874) (See under species heading);
Alvania aeoliae Palazzi, 1988: Italy: Cannizzaro, Catania, Sicily 43 m depth, 16 sh (BA), 30 m depth, 5 sh (BA); Salina I., Sicily, 35 m depth, vii.2002, >500 sh (BA);
Alvania algeriana (Monterosato, 1877): Algeria: Algiers, 6 syntypes (MCZR–M–22182 Monterosato coll. ex Joly); Algiers, 5 sh (MCZR–M–22182 Monterosato coll. ex Joly);
Alvania aspera (Philippi, 1844): Slovenia: Portoroz, beached, 1980, 8 sh (BA); Greece: Zakynthos I. under stones 2-3 m depth viii.1990, 1 sh (BA);
Alvania schwartziana Brusina, 1866: Croatia: Zara (now Zadar), 4 syntypes (MCZR–M–22326, Monterosato coll. ex Brusina); Pago (now Pag, near Zadar), 8 sh (BA); Starigrad Paklenica, Zadar, 6 m depth, 29 sh (EQ); Italy: “Tegnùe” [reefs built by coralline algae, bryozoans, sponges and cnidarians, with hardened sediments, typical of shallow waters in the Gulf of Venice between 8 and 40 meters depth; the local fishermen word, meaning ‘withhold’, refers to the fishing nets frequently remaining entangled: see e.g. NEWTON & STEFANON, 1975], Chioggia, Venice, 20 m depth, 2 sh (EQ) (first record for Italy);
Alvania garrafensis Peñas & Rolán, 2008: only photographs of the holotype (MNCN 15.05/47516);
Alvania settepassii Amati & Nofroni, 1985: Italy: holotype (MCZR–M–TYPE00004/H) and 42 paratypes Secche di Tor Paterno, 45 m depth (BA); Civitavecchia, 25-30 m depth, 69 paratypes (BA); Secche di Torre Flavia, Ladispoli 26 m depth 1986, 3 sh (BA); Giglio I., 27-30 m depth, 16 sh (BA); S. Stefano I., 40 m depth, 1 sh (BA); Torre Astura, beached, 3 sh (BA); Nettuno, beached, 1982, 1 sh (BA); Torvaldaliga, Civitavecchia, 20-22 m depth, 250 sh (CS-PM); Sicily: Vendicari I., 28 m depth, 1 sh (BA); Croatia: Lastovo I. 38 m depth, 21 sh (BA); Greece: Crete, 960 m depth, 3 sh (AP);
Alvania bozcaadensis Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013: Turkey: Bozcaada I., 12 m depth, 2 paratypes (EQ); Bozcaada I., 8-12 m depth, 23 sh (EQ); Aydıncık, 4 sh (BA); Greece: Leros I., amidst fishing nets residuals, 1985, 5 sh (CS-PM); Analipsi, Astypalea 5-6 m depth, beached bioclastic sand, 2013, 3 sh (MO);
Alvania perversa F. Nordsieck, 1972: (See under species heading);
Alvania dorbignyi (Audouin, 1826): (See under species heading);
Alvania claudioi Buzzurro & Landini, 2007: Italy: Zannone I. 18 m depth, x.2004, 1 sh (BA); Zannone I., Approdo Romano, 35 m depth, xiv.2008, 11 sh (7 juv.) (EQ);
Alvania campanii Tisselli & Giunchi, 2013: Turkey: Bozcaada I., 12 m depth, 2 paratypes (EQ), Bozcaada I., 8 m depth, 2 sh (BA), 2 sh (CS-PM); Bozcaada I., 8-12 m depth, 12 sh (EQ);
Alvania colossophilus Oberling, 1970: 1 syntype (NMBE); Croatia: Lastovo I. 38 m depth, 31 sh (BA); Turkey: Kash, 26.v.1992, 50 m depth, 20 sh (BA); Aydıncık, 10 m depth ix.1990 41 sh (BA); Cyprus: Cape Greco, Protaras, xi.2011, 7 sh (BA); Macronisos, beached xii.1988, 2 sh (BA);
Alvania datchaensis Amati & Oliverio, 1987: holotype and paratypes: MCZR, BA, MO; Cyprus, Cape Greco, Protaras, ix.2011, 11 sh (BA); Turkey: Aydıncık 9-10 m depth 1990 86 sh (BA);
Alvania discors (Allan, 1818): Italy: Trieste, 1980, 1 sh (BA); Sant’Agostino, Civitavecchia, Rome, 0.50 m depth on *Posidonia oceanica* 1980, 26 sh (BA); Torre Astura, Rome 1976-77, 64 sh (BA); Porto Cesareo, 55 sh (BA); Sicily: Palermo, 166 sh (MCZR–M–22145); Ognina, 19 sh (MCZR–M–22306); Porto Palo di Capopassero, 6 sh (BA); Lampedusa I., Cala Calandra, 30 m depth, iv.1981, 29 sh (BA); Vendicari I., 28 m

depth, 7 sh (BA); Capo Asparano, 13 sh (BA); Canizzaro, 30 m depth, 1 sh (BA); Magnisi (SR), beached bioclastic sand, legit J.J. Oberling (13.iii.1970), 30 sh (BA); Pantelleria I., Scauri, 13 m depth, 45 sh (BA); Sardinia: unspecified locality, viii.1981, 14 sh (BA); Santa Caterina, 1978, 8 sh (BA); Calasetta S. Antioco, 10 sh (BA); Maddalena I., 1 sh (BA); Croatia: Trogyr viii.1989 5-6 m depth, 58 sh (BA); San Lorenzo, 6 m depth, 25 sh (BA); Umag, 1980, 200 sh (BA); France: Verghia, Ajaccio, Corsica, 3 m depth, 4 sh (BA); Greece: unspecified locality, 15 sh (BA); Zakinthos I., 2-3 m depth, 24 sh (BA); Turkey: Aydıncik, 15 sh. (BA); Malta: undefined locality, 81 sh (BA); undefined locality, 8 sh (BA); Algeria: Oran, viii.1977, 4 sh (BA); Tunisia: Gulf of Gabès, Kerkennah, beach, 1974, 25 sh (BA); Gulf of Gabès, Kerkennah, loc. Sidi Youssef, 49 sh (BA); Gulf of Gabès, Kerkennah, beach, 32 sh (BA); Gulf of Gabès, Kerkennah, loc. Sidi Youssef, vii.2015, 350 sh (BA);

Alvania montagui (Payraudeau, 1826): photographs of the 2 syntypes, Corsica (MNHN-IM-2000-27921);

Alvania lanciae (Calcara, 1845): lectotype (Amati, 2012) and numerous (>200) paralectotypes, Pantelleria I. (MZP-1935); lectotype (Amati, 2012) and 7 paralectotypes of *Alvania consociella* Monterosato, 1884, Corsica (MCZR-M-22159), 7 paralectotypes, Villefranche (Villefranche-sur-Mer) (MCZR-M-30126 cabinet of type material); France: St. Raphael 49 sh (MCZR-M-22183), original labels reading "*Alvania arguta* (ex Locard coll.)" and "*A. locardi* Monts. mss (ex Cazier coll.)"; Verghia, Ajaccio, Corsica, 3 m depth, viii.1988, 4 sh (BA); Suasset les Pins, v.1982, 2 sh (IN); Spain: Palamos, 1978-79, 2 sh (BA); undefined locality, 2 sh (IN); Sardinia: Cala Gonone, Dorgali, viii.2010, 40°16'58.34"N, 9°38'15.30"E, 0.50 m depth, 42 lv on brown algae, 273 lv and sh on *Posidonia oceanica* (BA); undefined locality, 30 sh (Fra Piero legit, 1863, Monterosato coll., MCZR-M-30056); undefined locality, 7 m depth, 7.viii.1981, 6 sh (BA); Carloforte, Calasapone, 1 m depth, bioclastic sand, viii.2009, 7 sh (BA); Calasetta S. Antioco, 1977, 22 sh (BA); 'Punta Cavallo' (=Capo Coda Cavallo), 30 sh (Fra Piero legit, 1903, Monterosato coll., MCZR-M-30057); S. Pietro I., 8 sh (IN); S. Pietro I., locality Punta, 1-4 m depth, ix.1986, 17 sh (BA); Gulf of Aranci, viii.1977, 42 sh (IN); Porto Ferro, Sassari, viii.1980, 20 sh (IN); Maddalena I., Punta Marginetto, 41°15'14.70"N, 9°24'49.26"E, iii.1980, 25 sh (BA); Costa Serena, 1.5 m depth, vii.1991, 5 sh (BA); Stintino, viii.1977, 110 sh (IN); Isola Piana, Cagliari, vii.1984, 35 sh (IN); Golfo Aranci, 1985, 154 sh (BA); Capo Pecora, Cagliari, 1-2 m depth, vii.1984, 56 sh (IN); Bocche di Bonifazi 100-200 m depth, 1977, 1 sh (IN); Sicily: Magnisi, 130 sh (MCZR-M-22168); Magnisi, beached bioclastic sand, legit Oberling (13.iii.1970), 10 sh (BA); Ognina, Siracusa, 10.x.1982, beached bioclastic sand, 16 sh (BA); Punta Asparano, Siracusa, ix.1985, 14 sh (BA); north of Trapani, xii.1981, 12 sh (IN); S. Giuliano, Trapani, iv.1983, 12 sh (IN); Siracusa, iv.1982, 7 sh (IN); Lampedusa I., viii.1984, 8 sh (IN); Pantelleria I., locality Scauri, 12 vi.1991, 13 m depth, 3 sh (BA); Italy: Porto Maurizio, Imperia, 22 sh (Sulliotti legit, Monterosato coll., MCZR-M-30117); Sanremo, Imperia, 6 sh (IN); 4 km NW of Capraia I., 140 m depth, 1978, 1 sh (MCZR-M ex Mauro Pizzini coll.); Baratti Gulf, Livorno 10 m depth, viii.1983, 4 sh (IN); Antignano, Livorno, 1.5 m depth *Posidonia oceanica* meadow on muddy bottom, viii.1978, 1 lv (BA); Giannutri I., 18 m depth, vi.1983, 1 sh (IN); Giannutri I., Grosseto 47 m depth, vi.1982, 1sh (IN); Sant'Agostino, Civitavecchia, Rome, 1977, beached bioclastic sand, 250 sh (IN); Marina di Sant'Agostino, Civitavecchia, Rome, 1978, 5 sh (BA); Santa Marinella, Rome, beached bioclastic sand, 1977, 13 sh (BA); Torre Astura, Nettuno, Rome, 1977, beached bioclastic sand, 10 sh (BA); Torre Astura, Nettuno, Rome, 1977, 4 sh (IN); Marina di S. Nicola, Rome, 23.ii.1978, 4 sh (MCZR-M ex Mauro Pizzini coll.); Gulf of Napoli, bioclastic sand, iii.1979, 1 sh (BA); Procida I., Napoli, 4.vi.1978, 1 sh (BA); Procida I., Napoli, ix.1981, 5 m depth, 39 sh, (IN); Scilla, Reggio Calabria, xii.1987, 1 m depth amidst algae on the pier, 5 lv (IN); Santa Trada, Reggio Calabria, 1987, 1 m depth, 4 sh (IN); Scilla, Reggio Calabria, viii.1987, 7 m depth, 4 sh (IN); Taranto, 2 sh (Monterosato coll., MCZR-M-30058); Croatia: Punte Bianche (Velirat 'Veli Rat', Dugi Otok) 83 sh

(MCZR-M-22168); Trogyr, viii.1989, 6 m depth in *Posidonia oceanica* meadow, 7 lv (BA); Salvo 1 sh, (BA); Salvo 40-60 m depth, 2 sh (IN); Umag, iii.1980, 82 sh (BA); Slovenia: Portoroz, 1977, beached bioclastic sand, 5 sh, (BA); Greece: undefined locality in the Ionian Sea, beached bioclastic sand, 18 sh (BA); Lagonissi, Athens, vi.1982, 25 sh (IN); Astypalea, 25 m depth, 5 sh (CS-PM); Mediterranean Sea, undefined localities, 6 sh (Monterosato coll., MCZR-M-30128).

Alvania fractospira Oberling, 1970: 1 syntype (NMBE); Croatia: Trogir, 6 m depth *Posidonia oceanica* meadow ix.1989, 2 sh (BA); Greece: undefined localities of the Ionian Sea, beached, 5 sh (BA).

Alvania lineata Risso, 1826: Spain: Fuengirola, 30 m depth, viii.1985, 45 sh (BA); Malaga, 5-10 m depth 11.xi.2009, 30 sh (BA); Tunisia: Gulf of Gabès, Kerkennah, 1974, 24 sh (BA); Gulf of Gabès, Kerkennah, loc. Sidi Youssef, vii.2015, 200 sh (BA); Sardinia: San Teodoro, 1 sh (BA); Cala Gonone, Dorgali, Sardinia 1 m depth, viii.2010, 25 lv (BA); Maddalena I., Sardinia 1989 24 m depth, 1 sh (BA); Gulf Aranci, Sardinia, 1985, 3 sh (BA); Oristano, Sardinia, viii.1978, 4 sh (BA); Cala Gonone, Dorgali, Sardinia 2-4 m depth, viii.2010, 61 sh (BA); Sicily: Salina I., 35 m depth, vii.2002, 500 sh (BA); Levanzo I., Punta Altarella 31 m depth, 3.vi.1991, 6 sh (BA); Marettimo I., Egadi, Sicily, 19 sh (BA); Ognina, Siracusa, Sicily, 13 sh (BA); Magnisi, Eastern Sicily, Beached, legit Oberling (13.iii.1970), 35 sh, (BA); Portopalo di Capo Passero, Sicily, 1 sh (BA); Lampedusa I., Capo Grecale, vii.2009 50 m depth 10 sh (BA); Cannizzaro, Catania, Sicily, 35/43 m depth, 61 sh (BA); Ognina, Siracusa, Sicily 1984, washing algae, 24 lv (BA); Lampedusa I., 30 m depth, 53 sh (BA); Lampedusa I., Cala Calandra 30 m depth, 30.iv.1991, 46 sh (BA); Vendicari I., 28 m depth, 23 sh (BA); Ragusa, Secca of Roventa, Sicily 27 m depth, vi.1989, 8 sh (BA); Marettimo I., Egadi I., 10 sh (BA); Malta: Malta I., beached bioclastic sand, 1 sh (BA); Italy: Giglio I. 27-36 m depth, 45 sh (BA); Capraia I. 200-280 m depth, 1979, 1 sh (BA); Torre Astura, Rome, 1977, 1 sh (BA); San Felice Circeo, Latina, 30 m depth, 10 sh (BA); Pozzano Reggio Calabria, 40 m depth, viii.1986, 1 sh (BA); Secche of Tor Paterno, Rome, 30 m depth, 1.x.1988, 4 sh (BA); Secche of Tor Paterno, Rome, 45 m depth, 18 sh (BA); Santo Stefano I., Ventotene I. 40 m depth, 14 sh (BA); Ventotene I., 1979, 25 sh (BA); Capraia I., Livorno 140-180 m depth, 1978, 16 sh (BA); Secca di Torre Flavia 26 m depth, 1986, 64 sh (BA); Scilla (RC), 41 m depth, 16.xii.2006 legit Marconcini, 48 sh (IN); Croatia: Umag, beached bioclastic sand, 73 sh (BA); Umag, 1978, 7 sh (BA); San Lorenzo, 5 sh (BA); Slovenia: Portoroz, beached bioclastic sand, 1 sh (BA); Greece: undefined locality, 29 sh (BA); Crete, 34 sh (MCZR-M-30127); Crete, beached bioclastic sand, 5 sh (BA); Mediterranean Sea, undefined localities, 75 sh (MCZR-M-22149);

Alvania elisae Margelli, 2001: Italy: 1 paratype, Capraia I., 2-15 m depth (CS-PM, ex M. A. Fontana Angioy coll., Rome); Capri I., unspecified depth, 7 sh (MCZR-M-30060); Elba I., Capo di Fonza, 25 m depth, 80 sh (EQ), 7 sh (BA); Elba I., Capo di Stella, 20 m depth, 13 sh (EQ); Elba I., 3 sh (MO).